

Invited review article

The role of silicate alteration in regulating marine carbon cycling

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ABSTRACT

Alteration of silicate phases in marine sediments is important for the global budget of carbon, silicon, and many other elements. Despite the growing recognition of in-situ marine silicate alteration (dissolution and formation), its global significance and controlling factors are still poorly understood. By compiling data from scientific drilling and applying numerical modelling, we investigate the interactions between two connected feedback loops: the particulate organic-inorganic carbon loop and the forward-reverse silicate weathering loop. By simulating early diagenetic sequences in the top tens of meters of sediments, we examined the saturation state and interactions of a wide range of silicate minerals. When organic matter is degraded at moderate rates, iron- and sulfate-reduction elevate porewater pH and create a condition that favours reverse weathering driven by the formation of smectite-group clay phases. Our simulations estimate an up to 10 % increase in DIC flux towards the oxic surface sediments with no substantial change in the alkalinity flux. On the other hand, fast organic matter degradation acidifies pore fluids in extended methanogenic zones and induces dissolution of silicates. Dissolution of several reactive silicate phases (mica, amphibole, and pyroxene groups) buffers porewater pH by effectively converting dissolved CO₂ to carbonate alkalinity and results in marine silicate weathering. Consequently, the total alkalinity flux towards oxic sediments increases by as much as 11 % under this condition. The analyses of a global database of pore fluid composition suggest dominant weathering of K- and Mg-containing silicate minerals that can be identified visually. Higher-than-seawater Mg concentrations were observed in almost all sites where total alkalinity is >56 meq/L, with Mg accounting for up to 40 % of the measured alkalinity. Modelling of this data compilation points to dissolution of Mg- and K-rich mica-group silicates as the primary cause for the elevated total alkalinity. The degree of TA excess seems to increase at sites with greater burial thermal history below the sulfate reduction zone with two trends observed among different continental margins. Such a relationship is however not always statistically significant due to the limited number of study sites in certain margins.

Organic matter degradation determines the overall level and flux of DIC as well as dissolved CO₂ in pore fluids, with DIC speciation is modulated through silicate alteration and carbonate authigenesis. As demonstrated by our numerical modelling, increasing organic matter degradation rate four-fold leads to 6.1 times higher fluxes of DIC and total alkalinity towards the oxic sediments, with marine silicate alteration contributing ca. 10–11 % of the changes in DIC fluxes (for reverse weathering) and total alkalinity fluxes (for silicate weathering). We further show that the amounts of DIC sequestered as authigenic carbonate in the methanogenic sediments due to marine silicate weathering could be substantially lower than previous estimates but depends highly on the type of reactive silicate phases weathered. As expected, reverse weathering increases fluxes of dissolved CO₂. However, an even greater increase in dissolved CO₂ flux is predicted when organic matter is rapidly degraded, despite the pH buffering from active marine silicate weathering. The C–Si coupling has the potential to modify fluxes of DIC, total alkalinity, and likely other major dissolved constituents between marine sediments and the overlying bottom seawater. However, interpreting the convoluted feedback between organic matter degradation, marine silicate alteration, and carbonate authigenesis requires integrated efforts that take field observations, theoretical consideration, and laboratory constraints into consideration.

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1. Introduction

Terrestrial silicate weathering and reverse weathering in the ocean are the most important processes regulating Earth's long-term CO₂ budget (Urey, 1956; White and Brantley, 1995; R. A. Berner, 1995; Kump and Arthur, 1997; Gislason and Oelkers, 2011; Maher and Chamberlain, 2014; Isson and Planavsky, 2018; Komar and Zeebe, 2021; Brantley et al., 2023). Reverse weathering, or clay formation driven by dissolution of cation-depleted silicate/silica (as compared to the clay produced), is considered to be a major sink for cations, such as Ca, K, and Mg, in the ocean and convert carbonate alkalinity to dissolved CO₂ (Mackenzie and Garrels, 1966; Rude and Aller, 1994; Michalopoulos and Aller, 1995; Farkas et al., 2024). The production of CO₂, a potent greenhouse gas, has been proposed to insulate the early Earth when the Sun luminosity is low, thus playing a role in Earth's climate through geologic time (Dunlea et al., 2017; Isson and Planavsky, 2018; Krisanssen-Totton and Catling, 2020; Baldermann et al., 2025). On the other hand, silicate weathering transforms CO₂ to carbonate alkalinity and acts as a source of cations to the ocean. As compared to the congruent carbonate weathering, the much slower incongruent dissolution of silicate minerals during weathering (Gislason and Oelkers, 2011) provides stabilising feedback that prevents the Earth CO₂ cycle from fluctuating dramatically with time (Colbourn et al., 2015). The produced cations and alkalinity promote the precipitation of carbonate minerals, sequestering carbon in marine sediments:

Such an interaction between silicate and carbonate was summarised by Urey (1956) as:

The Urey reaction represents a long-term sink for carbon as the residence time of carbonate is much longer than that of the dissolved inorganic carbon (DIC), the product of carbonate weathering (Gislason and Oelkers, 2011).

Traditionally, only the silicate weathering of aurally exposed igneous rocks such as granite and basalt have been considered significant enough to be counted towards global weathering rates (Gaillardet et al., 1999; Dessert et al., 2003; Moon et al., 2014; Colbourn et al., 2015). The contribution of low-temperature weathering of submarine basalt is thought to be small (Table 1) with marine weathering of disseminated lithogenic silicates in marine sediments rarely considered in early carbon and silicon budget estimates (Wollast and Mackenzie, 1983; Gaillardet et al., 1999; Dessert et al., 2003; Goudie and Viles, 2012; Moon et al., 2014; Frings et al., 2016; Sutton et al., 2018; Tréguer et al., 2021) except for some more recent studies (e.g., Isson et al., 2020; Wallmann et al., 2023; Rahman and Trower, 2023). Such a view is however challenged by the observations of lithogenic silicate dissolution in the ocean column (Jeandel and Oelkers, 2015) and by disseminated

volcanic phenocrysts alteration in marine sediments (White et al., 2011; Luo et al., 2020; Hong et al., 2020b; Meister et al., 2022), which have the potential to neutralize dissolved CO₂. It has also been proposed that, in anoxic marine sediments, weathering of disseminated lithogenic silicates could be driven by the acidic pore fluids that result from organic matter fermentation (Aloisi et al., 2004; Torres et al., 2004; Wallmann et al., 2008; Scholz et al., 2013; Solomon et al., 2014; Kim et al., 2016; Meister et al., 2022). In all these studies, the actual silicate mineral(s) involved have been inferred without confirmation through field and/or laboratory observations. The reported carbonate precipitation resulting from marine silicate weathering (Torres et al., 2020) can potentially be summarised in an analogous fashion to the Urey reaction (e.g., Eq. (3) in Torres et al. (2020), cf. Eq. (2)), assuming that dissolution of anorthite is the primary weathering phase (Wallmann et al., 2008; Solomon et al., 2014). Such an assumption, however, has never been tested and the exact silicate phase(s) involved is unknown.

As the primary disseminated silicate phase responsible for the observed weathering has only been inferred, various authors have used the general term "cation-rich silicate" (as opposed to the precipitating cation-poor silicate phases) to replace the CaSiO₃ in Eq. (2) when describing the marine version of the Urey reaction (Wallmann et al., 2008; Solomon et al., 2014). The dissolved CO₂ that drives dissolution of the "cation-rich silicate" (i.e. the left-hand side of Eq. (2)) is produced from organic matter remineralization (Wallmann et al., 2008). This suggests a stronger coupling between marine silicate weathering and particulate organic carbon cycle (Wallmann et al., 2008; Farkas et al., 2024), which has not received enough in-depth consideration. Rate estimates for global CO₂-fixation through marine silicate weathering have been made for the ocean (Jeandel and Oelkers, 2015) and sediments (Wallmann et al., 2008, 2023a; Torres et al., 2020). Taken together with carbon uptake by oceanic crust alteration, the overall marine silicate weathering rate could be at least 20 % (Table 1) of that for the terrestrial silicate weathering, the later likely overestimated due to cation exchange reactions (Tipper et al., 2021). In addition, the CO₂-neutralizing power of terrestrial silicate weathering can be offset by the accompanying oxidation of fossil organic carbon (Zondervan et al., 2023). Overall, marine weathering of disseminated lithogenic silicates may play a more important role in regulating global CO₂ than previously considered.

Nonetheless, the estimates of marine silicate weathering are not without caveats. First and foremost, previous estimates assume that methanogenesis operates through a tight coupling (i.e. no material loss in between the reactions) of glucose fermentation and hydrogenotrophic CO₂ reduction that produces equal amounts of CO₂ and CH₄ (Wallmann et al., 2008; Akam et al., 2023). The rate of CO₂ consumption through silicate weathering in anoxic sediments has thus been equated to global methane production (Wallmann et al., 2008; Torres et al., 2020). Another underlining assumption is the postulated unlimited supply of a yet undefined reactive silicate mineral to the global methanogenic sediment. The estimate through these assumptions sets an important foundation but it is also a first-order value that should be revised further. An obvious aspect for improvement is a better understanding of the environmental controls on marine silicate alteration. The occurrence of marine silicate weathering, as indicated by high porewater total alkalinity (TA), is not universal in anoxic marine sediment that present other indicators of silicate dissolution (see later for our data compilation). These observations suggest the role of additional controlling factors besides the supply (and pathways) of organic matter and silicates to the sediments.

The fraction of marine silicate-neutralized CO₂ being fixed as carbonate minerals (right-hand side of the Urey reaction or Eq. (2)) is currently unconstrained. Akam et al. (2023) assumes that half of carbon sequestered in authigenic carbonate minerals is from marine silicate weathering without an explicit justification for such a ratio. Based on a case study from Sakhalin Island, Wallmann et al. (2008) estimated that one-third of the alkalinity ends up in the carbonate mineral phases. The

Table 1

CO₂ consumption rates through terrestrial and marine silicate weathering.

Silicate weathering		Rate (Tmol C/ yr)
Terrestrial		11.7 ^a 9.86–14.01 ^b
Marine	Terrigenous particulate dissolution in ocean	0.3–3.2 ^c
	Submarine dissolution of disseminated lithogenic silicates in anoxic sediments	1–4 ^d
	Alteration of oceanic crust	1.5–2.4 ^e
	<u>Total</u>	<u>2.8–9.6</u>

^a Gaillardet et al. (1999).

^b Moon et al. (2014) and Dessert et al. (2003).

^c Jeandel and Oelkers (2015).

^d Torres et al. (2020).

^e Alt and Teagle (1999a).

optimistic ratio from Akam et al. (2023) results in a burial that is about 5 % of the global carbon burial through both organic carbon and carbonate (Table 1 in Akam et al. (2023)). The robustness of this estimate awaits further investigation. Despite the various caveats in estimating marine silicate weathering contribution, its potential deserves consideration given the prevalent occurrence of silicate minerals and disseminated volcanic phenocrysts in marine sediments (Mahony et al., 2020), and their submarine weathering commonly occurring along the continental margins (Rex and Martin, 1966; Parham, 1969; Fisk et al., 1998; White et al., 2011; Scholz et al., 2013; Zhu et al., 2016; Sample et al., 2017; Luo et al., 2020; Hong et al., 2020b).

In this contribution, we define marine silicate alteration as a combined reaction of silicate dissolution (i.e. weathering) and clay formation (i.e. reverse weathering) in marine sediments. We will focus on the dissolution of disseminated lithogenic silicate minerals and exclude the weathering of basaltic oceanic crusts along the mid-ocean ridge that have been well documented elsewhere (Fisk et al., 1998; Alt and Teagle, 1999; Torres et al., 2015). We first review the principles and kinetics of marine silicate alteration (Section 2). Then, we discuss how silicate alteration is coupled to the carbon cycle in early diagenetic environments by employing a numerical model (Section 3). To compare the results from our numerical modelling with field data, we select 48 sites for which porewater composition and/or isotopic signatures are indicative of marine silicate alteration (Section 4). Collectively, we address the following aspects:

- What group(s) of silicate minerals is/are mainly responsible for marine silicate alteration?
- What environmental factors determine the occurrence and rate of marine silicate alteration?
- How does marine silicate alteration affect carbon cycling in sediments and fluxes towards the seafloor?

2. Setting the stage- a critical review of silicate alteration in marine environments

2.1. Major silicate mineral groups

There are six major types of silicate minerals (Table 2) but not all of them are relevant when it comes to the discussion of marine silicate alteration.

In classifying silicate minerals by their origin, two groups of silicate minerals are relevant to the discussion of disseminate lithogenic silicates in marine environments. The first group of silicates are the rock-forming primary minerals that are physically weathered on land and transported

Table 2

Major classification of silicate minerals. Underlined mineral groups are modelled for their saturation under different early diagenetic conditions in Section 3.2. See Supplementary Table 3 for the full list of mineral names.

Structure	Major group	Chemical formula	Example
Independent tetrahedral	Nesosilicates	$[\text{SiO}_4]^{4-}$	<u>Olivine</u> , Zircon, Garnet group
Double tetrahedral	Sorosilicates	$[\text{Si}_2\text{O}_7]^{6-}$	Epidote group
Rings	Cyclosilicates	$[\text{Si}_n\text{O}_{3n}]^{2n-}$	Melilite group <u>Pyroxene</u> group (single), <u>Amphibole</u> group (double)
Single or double chain	Inosilicates	$[\text{Si}_n\text{O}_{11n}]^{6n-}$	<u>Mica</u> group, Chlorite group,
Sheet/layered	Phyllosilicates	$[\text{Si}_{2n}\text{O}_{5n}]^{2n-}$	Clay minerals (<u>kaolinite</u> , <u>illite</u> group, <u>smectite</u> group, and <u>vermiculite</u>) <u>Feldspar</u> group (alkali feldspar and plagioclase), <u>quartz</u> , <u>zeolite</u> group
3D framework	Tectosilicates	$[\text{Al}_x\text{Si}_y\text{O}_{(2x+2y)}]^{x-}$	

to the marine environments via rivers, air, and/or additional sea bottom (horizontal) processes, such as turbidity flows and mass transport events (Warr, 2022). The mineral composition of this group depends on the source regions, and could be of mafic/ultramafic (olivine, orthopyroxene, anorthite and plagioclase (e.g., Brady and Gíslason, 1997)), phenocrysts in volcanic ashes deposited on the seafloor (Nakagawa and Ohba, 2002), or felsic (Na- and K-rich minerals such as the alkali feldspar) composition.

The second group, and arguably the most abundant type of silicate minerals in hemipelagic sediments, comprises the clay minerals (Warr, 2022). Clay minerals can be defined as a category of hydrated phyllosilicates (i.e. sheet/layered silicate, Table 2) whose structural regularity does not extend beyond ~ 1.4 nm (Theng, 2012). In hemipelagic sediment, clays include both the terrestrial weathering products transported to the ocean and/or the clay minerals that form in-situ (Warr, 2022). Clay formation from reverse weathering has been widely documented in sediments from the abyssal plain (Santiago Ramos et al., 2018; Luo et al., 2022; Du et al., 2022; Steiner et al., 2022), continental shelf (Ehlert et al., 2016; Pickering et al., 2020; Ward et al., 2022; Geilert et al., 2023), to coastal systems (Michalopoulos and Aller, 1995; Krause et al., 2017; Pickering et al., 2023). The references provided here are far from complete but we cite them to highlight some more recent publications.

2.2. An overview of marine silicate alteration: Silicate dissolution and clay formation

2.2.1. Silicate weathering as interfacial dissolution of cation-rich silicate phases

Being a fundamental process across Earth's surface, the definition of chemical silicate weathering varies depending on the disciplines. Viers et al. (2007) state that chemical silicate minerals are "weathered" due to the far-from-equilibrium status of these silicates when compared to the conditions in which these silicate minerals originated and are currently deposited. The exact processes involved during weathering of these silicates, i.e. the mechanistic definition of "silicate weathering", relevant to our discussion here require some clarifications. On a macroscopic level, chemical weathering is often linked to partial or incongruent dissolution of silicate minerals (Chou and Wollast, 1985; Mast et al., 1990; Viers et al., 2007). The destruction of rocks and minerals turns them into smaller pieces and can result in changes of rock composition (Jackson and Sherman, 1953; Wilson, 2004; Macheyski et al., 2020). The critical chemical process involved is the *preferential dissolution* of minerals at an *interfacial* level between the mineral surface and the ambient solution (Casey and Ludwig, 1995; Liu et al., 2006; Schott et al., 2009). Such a preferential dissolution could be crystallographically controlled (Wilson, 2004) with other environmental factors, such as pH, temperature, fluid composition, surface area, and the presence of inhibitors or catalysts, playing important roles (Oelkers et al., 1994; Blum and Stillings, 1995; Brantley and Chen, 1995; Brady and Gíslason, 1997; Brantley et al., 2023). Below we review a few important considerations needed to parameterize silicate dissolution kinetics.

The rate-limiting step of single oxide/hydroxide minerals is adsorption of proton or ligand onto a mineral surface (Lasaga, 1995; Pokrovsky et al., 2006). However, for the case of multi-oxide minerals, dissolution can be promoted by the exchange between proton and cation across the mineral-solution interfaces (Oelkers et al., 2009). Therefore, dissolution of these minerals is highly dependent on the solutes present and their concentrations (Oelkers et al., 1994; Oelkers and Schott, 2001). Silicate dissolution can be described as a ligand-exchange reaction (Casey and Ludwig, 1995). A ligand is an ion or molecule (function group) that binds the central metal atom to form a coordination complex (Burdge and Overby, 2012). The binding involves formal donation of one or more electrons and thus ligands can be considered as Lewis bases (Cotton et al., 1999; Fischer et al., 2013). According to Casey and Ludwig (1995), there exist two types of dissolution mechanisms: proton-promoted dissolution and ligand-promoted dissolution for acidic

conditions. In proton-promoted dissolution, when a proton binds the hydroxide ion at the mineral surface, it modifies its charge distribution and weakens one of the bonds in the targeted hydroxide ion. This results in detachment/dissociation of the entire complex. In the ligand-promoted case, ligands, as Lewis bases, can replace the hydroxyl site and directly associate the metals to form a new type of ligand that is easier to dissociate from the bulk mineral surface (Casey and Ludwig, 1995).

These two dissolution pathways, proton-promoted and ligand-promoted, are not independent and may occur sequentially or in parallel. For example, Liu et al. (2006) proposed a two-stage dissolution model for olivine. In the first proton-promoting stage, protonation breaks the Mg–O bonds in olivine and allows water molecules (the ligand) to coordinate with Mg. This results in the exposure of silica rich surfaces that are available for ligand exchange. This second ligand-promoting stage of olivine dissolution is slower than the first proton-promoting stage and can thus be the rate limiting step of the entire dissolution process (Casey and Westrich, 1992). The model of ligand exchange for silicate dissolution seems to work for inosilicates (e.g., pyroxenes and amphiboles; Brantley and Chen, 1995; Oelkers and Schott, 2001), some phyllosilicates (Nagy, 1995; Kiczka et al., 2010), and to some extent for feldspar (Amrhein and Suarez, 1988; Blum and Stillings, 1995; Brantley and Stillings, 1996). Organic ligands only substantially increase smectite dissolution rates when the concentration is over millimolar level (Golubev et al., 2006). Through ab initio simulations, Schliemann and Churakov (2021) show that, besides the proton-promoted and ligand-promoted steps, there is an addition proton transfer step during phyllosilicate dissolution that is applicable to the 2:1 phyllosilicate group over wide conditions.

The overall rate of silicate dissolution can thus be approximated by that of the rate-limiting step, i.e., the ligand exchange. Transient state theory was developed to account for the energy barrier from the rate-limiting step that needs to be overcome (Lasaga, 1995). The theory has been very successfully applied to quantify rates of mineral precipitation and dissolution. The theory can also be formulated following a Langmuir adsorption isotherm model (e.g., Blum and Lasaga, 1988; Cama and Ganor, 2006). Other mechanistic models for silicate dissolution were also developed over the past decades with their own assumptions and limitations (Dove et al., 2005; Lüttge, 2006; Cama and Ganor, 2006). For the numerical model that will be discussed in Section 3, we use a general rate expression given by Lasaga (1995):

$$R = k_0 A_{min} e^{-\frac{E_a}{RT}} X_{H,ads}^{n_{H,ads}} g(I) \prod_i X_{i,ads}^{n_i} f(\Delta G_r) \quad (3)$$

k_0 : intensive rate constant including all the pre-exponential terms from Arrhenius term.

A_{min} : reactive mineral surface of the mineral.

E_a : apparent activation energy of the overall reaction.

R : ideal gas constant.

T : temperature.

$X_{H,ads}$: the activity of the adsorbed proton on the mineral surface.

$n_{H,ads}$: stoichiometric number of protons.

$X_{i,ads}$: the activities of the adsorbed solution species onto mineral surface.

n_i : stoichiometric number of the solution species.

$g(I)$: dependence of solution ionic strength.

$f(\Delta G_r)$: deviation from equilibrium, which is defined by the mole fraction of adsorbed species and the solution composition and can be described by the transient state theory (see Lasaga et al. (1994) for discussion of this term).

A more sophisticated expression, taking into account whether the solution condition is acidic, neutral, or basic, has been applied to existing laboratory results for internally consistent mineral dissolution databases (Hermanská et al., 2022, 2023).

To better connect with carbon cycling, we define chemical silicate

weathering in marine sediments as meeting all of the following criteria:

- Chemical silicate weathering is defined as interfacial dissolution of silicate minerals driven by the acidity produced through early diagenetic reactions in the environment.
- The acidity that drives chemical silicate weathering comes from carbonic acid.
- The product of chemical silicate weathering includes aqueous bicarbonate/carbonate ions, various cations, and dissolved silica.

The first part of this definition equates chemical silicate weathering to *acidity-driven silicate dissolution* (a in Fig. 1). Silicate dissolution can occur under basic conditions at comparable rates for certain minerals (Brady and Walther, 1989; Oelkers et al., 1994; White and Brantley, 1995; Bagheri et al., 2022), and driven by molecular water, and/or metallic/organic ligands (Casey et al., 1993; Bennett and Casey, 1994; Casey and Ludwig, 1995; Liu et al., 2006; Oelkers et al., 2018). Therefore, it is important to differentiate the acidity-driven dissolution from the alternative pathways when it comes to relating silicate weathering to the CO_2 budget.

The second part of our definition ties silicate weathering to carbon cycling and consequently, climate (Kump and Arthur, 1997). The narrow definition above, that considers only *CO₂-driven silicate dissolution* excludes silicate dissolution driven by organic acids or other types of acid that do not involve carbon uptake. For example, DiPietro (2013) defined chemical weathering as driven by “pouring acid on a rock” without specifying what kind of acid. Such a broad definition including all *acidity-driven silicate dissolution* is appropriate when assessing, for example, the overall Si contribution from chemical silicate weathering (Sun et al., 2016). However, it may overestimate CO_2 -neutralizing power during silicate weathering. The strict definition we use here also helps to eliminate the confusion between (forward) silicate weathering and *reverse* (silicate) weathering. The word “reverse” refers to the opposite effect on carbon species compared to weathering (see Section 2.2.2) but not necessary the type of silicate diagenesis involved. In other words, reverse weathering consumes carbonate alkalinity (i.e., aqueous bicarbonate and carbonate ions) and has a *net* production of carbonic acid ($H_2CO_{3(aq)}$) that could increase the partial pressure of $CO_{2(aq)}$ in an aqueous environment or release of CO_2 gas to the atmosphere (c in Fig. 1).

The last part of our definition specifies the product of chemical silicate weathering to be in the form of dissolved species. In other words, our definition of silicate weathering is congruent and excludes the formation of secondary mineral phases, such as carbonate and clay minerals. Arguably, the overall processes associated with silicate weathering are hardly congruent in nature. However, our approach is practically advantageous in that it allows for the maximum CO_2 -neutralizing capacity to be accurately assessed without complications from other secondary processes. To illustrate this, in Table 3 we list examples of the various secondary clay products that can derive from anorthite dissolution, a primary silicate mineral commonly referred to in studies of marine silicate weathering (Wallmann et al., 2008, 2023a; Solomon et al., 2014). Table 3 shows how much CO_2 is being converted or produced in each of the possible scenarios. It becomes apparent that, depending on the type of clay mineral formed, dissolution of one mole of anorthite can convert one mole of CO_2 (Eq. (5) and Eq. (6) in Table 3), 0.67 mol of CO_2 (Eq. (7) in Table 3), or even produce CO_2 (Eq. (8) in Table 3). This large difference arises from the cation imbalance among the different authigenic silicate minerals formed; montmorillonite and nontronite contain more cations than kaolinite (Fig. 1), and thus additional dissolved iron, magnesium will be needed from solution to form this authigenic minerals. This in turn changes the aqueous carbonate speciation to achieve charge balance (pathway a in Fig. 1). From a quantitative point of view (i.e. numerical modelling, Section 3), it is straightforward to separate anorthite dissolution (i.e. weathering) from the formation of secondary clay phases (thus reverse weathering), as

Fig. 1. Illustration of marine silicate alteration and its association with CO₂ production/neutralisation capability as well as dissolved cation budget. The greyscale illustrates the cation-to-Si ratios (Supplementary Table 3). For the different silicate minerals that will be discussed in later sections, their respective ratios are indicated as the numbers in the parentheses (a) Marine silicate weathering (Eq. (4)), or dissolution of cation-rich silicates, generates dissolved Si (dSi), aluminium (dAl), and other cations. The excess positive charges from the cations released leads to production of carbonate alkalinity to maintain charge balance. The high solute concentrations lead to (b) formation of cation-poor or (c) cation-rich secondary clay minerals depending on fluid composition and clay mineral saturation. The type of clay mineral formed thus has an impact on the overall CO₂ neutralizing power as exemplified in Table 3. (d) Dissolution of cation-poor silicate or opal, though does not release additional cations, it increases the concentrations of dSi and/or dAl that will also lead to formation clay minerals and thus convert carbonate alkalinity to H₂CO_{3(aq)}.

Table 3
Different variety of anorthite dissolution[‡].

Anorthite dissolution pathways	ΔAlk [±]
$\text{CaAl}_2\text{Si}_2\text{O}_8(s) \text{ (anorthite)} + 2\text{H}_2\text{CO}_{3(aq)} + 6\text{H}_2\text{O}(l) \text{ (5)}$ $\rightarrow \text{Ca}^{2+} + 2\text{H}_4\text{SiO}_4(aq) + 2\text{Al}(\text{OH})_3(aq) + 2\text{HCO}_3^-$	2
$\text{CaAl}_2\text{Si}_2\text{O}_8(s) \text{ (anorthite)} + 2\text{H}_2\text{CO}_{3(aq)} + \text{H}_2\text{O}(l) \text{ (6)}$ $\rightarrow \text{Al}_2\text{Si}_2\text{O}_5(\text{OH})_4(s) \text{ (kaolinite)} + \text{Ca}^{2+} + 2\text{HCO}_3^-$	2
$\text{CaAl}_2\text{Si}_2\text{O}_8(s) \text{ (anorthite)} + 1.34\text{H}_2\text{CO}_{3(aq)} + 2\text{H}_4\text{SiO}_4(aq) + 0.33\text{H}_2\text{O}(l) \text{ (7)}$ $\rightarrow \text{Ca}_{0.33}\text{Al}_2(\text{Si}_4\text{O}_{10})(\text{OH})_2 \cdot n\text{H}_2\text{O}(s) \text{ (montmorillonite)} + 0.67\text{Ca}^{2+} + 1.34\text{HCO}_3^- + (4-n)\text{H}_2\text{O}(l)$	1.34
$\text{CaAl}_2\text{Si}_2\text{O}_8(s) \text{ (anorthite)} + 10.3\text{HCO}_3^- + 3.7\text{Fe}^{3+} + 0.1\text{Mg}^{2+} + 5\text{H}_4\text{SiO}_4(aq) \text{ (8)}$ $\rightarrow \text{Ca}_{0.5}(\text{Si}_7\text{Al}_{0.8}\text{Fe}_{0.2})(\text{Fe}_{3.5}\text{Al}_{0.4}\text{Mg}_{0.1})\text{O}_{20}(\text{OH})_4 \cdot n\text{H}_2\text{O}(s) \text{ (nontronite)} + 0.5\text{Ca}^{2+} + 0.8\text{Al}(\text{OH})_3(aq) + 10.3\text{H}_2\text{CO}_{3(aq)} + (0.8-n)\text{H}_2\text{O}(l) + 0.05\text{H}_2\text{O}(aq) + 0.8\text{H}_2\text{O}(l)$	-10.3

n in Eq. (7) & Eq. (8) represents the moles of structural water in montmorillonite and nontronite, respectively.

[‡] References for the various anorthite dissolution reactions are (Hayes and Boles, 1992; Bjørlykke, 1998; Brosse et al., 1999; Morad et al., 2000) for kaolinite and (Cole and Shaw, 1983; Ilgen and Cygan, 2016; Baker and Neill, 2017) for montmorillonite and nontronite.

[±] Changes of alkalinity (ΔAlk) represent net production (positive) or consumption (negative) of alkalinity (equivalent/mol anorthite). This is also equal to the mole of H₂CO_{3(aq)} neutralized for every mole of anorthite dissolved.

transient state theory is only applicable to elementary reactions (Lasaga and Kirkpatrick, 1981; Cama and Ganor, 2006) such as the ones we focus on. We can thus summarize silicate weathering as an elementary reaction of:¹

Al(OH)_{3(aq)}, or the predominant dissolved species of aluminium in seawater, is separated from other major cations in Eq. (4) due its low concentration in solution and potentially stronger affinity to sediment particles (such as clay minerals) relative to other cations (Walker et al., 1988; Bruland and Lohan, 2006). Precipitation of Al(OH)_{3(aq)} is tightly coupled to silicate dissolution (Eq. (4)) but should be regarded as a

¹ The following general rules will be applied when formulating chemical equations throughout: (a) The most abundant species under seawater pH will be used (e.g., HCO₃⁻ for aqueous carbonate and Al(OH)_{3(aq)} for dissolved aluminium). (b) Proton (H⁺) will be represented by carbonic acid whenever suitable. The subscript *s*, *l*, *aq* denote *solid*, *liquid*, and *aqueous*, respectively.

separated elementary reaction.

2.2.2. Clay formation and reverse weathering

Unlike weathering that drives dissolution of silicate minerals, authigenesis of cation-rich secondary clays produces CO₂ (c in Fig. 1):

Similar to silicate dissolution (Eq. (4)), clay formation is also expressed as an elementary reaction. This reaction was termed reverse weathering for its capacity to produce H₂CO_{3(aq)} from other aqueous carbonate species, i.e. the opposite of weathering (cf. Eq. (4)). The dissolved silica, or silicic acid, in Eq. (9) can be sourced from the dissolution of siliceous organisms (McManus et al., 1995; Van Cappellen et al., 2002; Ehlert et al., 2016), volcanic glass (Fisk et al., 1998; Oelkers, 2001; White et al., 2011; Galezcka et al., 2014), and/or other reactive sedimentary Si phases that have less cations than the clay being formed (such as *d* in Table 3). Dissolution of biogenic silica is deemed as the primary source of dissolved silica in porewater and the most important driver sustaining reverse weathering (Baldermann et al., 2025 and the

references in). Clay formation also accompanies silicate weathering, which reduces CO₂-neutralizing capacity, as exemplified in Table 3. The precipitation of clay minerals occurs via two major pathways in solution: neof ormation (i.e. direct precipitation from solution) and transformation from pyroclastic or detrital precursors (Pozo and Calvo, 2018). The rate-limiting step of clay formation is nucleation, which could occur with or without a pre-existing solid phase (i.e., *heterogeneously* or *homogeneously*, respectively), with different energy demands for it to be thermodynamically feasible.

In order for nucleation to be plausible from a solution (i.e. *homogeneous* nucleation), the barrier of activation energy for making bonds (ΔG_{bond}) and creating surface (ΔG_{surf}) needs to be surpassed (Stumm, 1992):

$$\Delta G_{nu} = \Delta G_{bond} + \Delta G_{surf} \quad (10)$$

where ΔG_{nu} refers to the Gibbs free energy of reaction for nucleation. As ΔG_{bond} is always negative (Van Cappellen, 1991), for nucleation to be spontaneous, ΔG_{surf} has to be small enough so that ΔG_{nu} is negative. Such a condition can be achieved if the radius of the newly formed nucleus is large enough and/or if the degree of oversaturation, defined as the ion activity product (IAP) over the equilibrium constant (denoted as K_{sp}), is sufficiently high.

Unlike homogeneous nucleation that only involves the interfacial properties between water and the newly formed mineral nucleus, *heterogeneous* nucleation, or formation of a nucleus in association with another pre-existing solid, is more complicated but often thermodynamically more favourable than the homogeneous process (Steeffel and Van Cappellen, 1990; Van Cappellen, 1991; Stumm, 1992). The pre-existing solid acts as a catalyst to lower the activation energy barrier. Under an ideal situation of high interfacial energy between the substrate and water, one can express the interactions between the water surface (w), mineral nucleus (c), and substrate (s , where new precipitation occurs) as follows (Van Cappellen, 1991):

$$\Delta G_{surf} = \bar{\gamma}_{cw}(A_{cw} - A_{cs}) \quad (11)$$

where A is surface area and $\bar{\gamma}_{cw}$ is interfacial energy resulting from the tension between mineral nuclei. By considering the different nuclei geometry, one can then determine the critical radius so that ΔG_{surf} in Eq. (11) is small enough to allow for ΔG_{nu} in Eq. (10) to be negative.

It is known that some of the clay minerals are not in equilibrium with the conditions present in shallow marine sediments (Morse and Casey, 1988; Steefel and Van Cappellen, 1990; Galán, 2006). Whereas metastable clay phases may be predicted to be thermodynamically unfavourable, their formation has been observed to occur in shallow marine sediments (Galán, 2006). This is generally explained by the Ostwald step rule (or ripening) that predicts the formation of different metastable (clayey) phases as a transient step form in sequence towards the most stable (clay) minerals (Ostwald, 1897). The metastable phases, in general, have lower interfacial energies ($\bar{\gamma}_{cw}$ in Eq. (11)) as compared to the stable phases (Steeffel and Van Cappellen, 1990; Van Cappellen, 1991) and thus are easier to nucleate once the solution reaches oversaturation. The newly formed fine-grained metastable phases could serve as templates for the formation of a more stable phase (i.e. heterogeneous nucleation) (Steeffel and Van Cappellen, 1990) that brings the solution composition towards the equilibrium of the stable phase at the expense of dissolving the metastable phases.

A classic case of the Ostwald step rule is the transition from opal-A to opal-CT and then to quartz. Solid silica, or SiO_{2(s)}, is present in natural environments as amorphous silica (or opal-A) or various better crystallized phases (e.g., opal-A', opal-CT, and quartz). Certain siliceous organisms precipitate biogenic opal-A (De La Rocha and Conley, 2017), while abiotic formation of opal-A has also reported (e.g., hot-spring deposits, or sinters, Lynne and Campbell (2004)). Upon sediment burial, the amorphous opal-A dissolves and re-precipitates as opal-CT with an intermediate stage of opal-A' (Hein et al., 1978; Williams

et al., 1985). During this transition, surface area and particle size have critical controls on the solubility of the different opal phases (Williams and Crerar, 1985; Eberl et al., 1990; Cardew, 2023) (Eq. (10) and Eq. (11)). Solubility of the different opal phases is also pH-dependent in a basic solution (pH > 9) (see Section 7.2 and Supplementary Table 2 for more information). This sequential opal transition is an example of Ostwald ripening, or the formation of larger crystal/polymers/particles that build from the dissolution of smaller crystal/polymers/particles (Ostwald, 1897; Steefel and Van Cappellen, 1990). A closed-system condition is required for dissolved silica to accumulate and thus allow the ripening of opal-A, opal-CT, into the micro-quartz (see review in Hesse, 1989; Hesse and Schacht, 2011). Kaolinite formation under low temperature conditions is another example of the Ostwald step rule (Tazaki, 1986; Steefel and Van Cappellen, 1990). Formation of poorly-ordered clay precursors that later evolve into meta-halloysite, gibbsite, and/or even kaolinite has been documented and predicted by models (Parham, 1969; Tazaki, 1986; Steefel and Van Cappellen, 1990).

In recent years, the Ostwald step rule has been criticized for its validity because a general proof for this rule is still lacking (Cardew, 2023). The transition of metastable to stable mineral phases may not happen in sequence as Ostwald originally proposed. On the contrary, formation of all meta-stable/stable phases occur in parallel (Morse and Casey, 1988) but the disappearance of phases happens in sequence according to the order of metastability (Cardew, 2023). The meta-stable clayey phase is the fastest to form, as compared to the stable phases, but it is also the earliest to disappear when concentration drops below the meta-stable phase saturation.

Our mechanistic elaboration highlights the importance of surface kinetics in terms of clay formation as well as incorporating clay mineral evolution from its metastable precursor in marine sediments. The interaction between clay minerals and other sediment particles has the potential to impact global carbon cycling, as recently reviewed (Warr, 2022). Below, we summarize the two aspects that are more relevant to our discussion. Heterogeneous clay authigenesis can form weathered crusts that halt surface silicate alteration on land (Berner, 1995). Whether this is also the case for marine silicate alteration is unclear; nonetheless, field/laboratory experiments suggest that precipitation of clay-like phases onto diatom frustules may make diatoms more resistant to dissolution (McManus et al., 1995; Loucaides et al., 2010). If such heterogeneous precipitation of clay-like phases is associated with the dissolution of silicate minerals (i.e. silicate weathering), the newly precipitated secondary phases may reduce the contact between the weathering silicate minerals and the H₂CO_{3(aq)} in ambient porewater, consequently lowering weathering rates. Another potential implication of the surface kinetics of clay minerals is their ability to bind dissolved organic compounds (Blattmann et al., 2019; Churchman et al., 2020; Warr, 2022). As degradation of dissolved organic compounds primarily controls H₂CO_{3(aq)} production (e.g., glucose hydrolysis and acetate fermentation, Canfield et al. (2005)) and thus impact marine silicate weathering rates (Wallmann et al., 2008), additional sinks of these dissolved organic components (through clay mineral complexation) may again suppress silicate weathering.

3. Si—C coupling in early diagenetic marine sediments

3.1. A transport-reaction framework: Particulate organic matter degradation, early diagenesis, and silicate alteration

Marine silicate alteration creates an excess (through silicate dissolution) or deficit (through clay formation) of dissolved cations, which in turn requires the production or consumption of negative charges to maintain charge balance. In marine environments, the charge balance is regulated by a series of weak acid-based pairs, primarily the exchanges among carbonic acid, bicarbonate, and carbonate ions (Supplementary Table 2). In turn, changes in aquatic carbonate speciation determine the buffer capacity of solution, i.e. how sensitive the solution pH is to

changes in composition. The coupled effects of cation budget, carbonate speciation, and pH resulting from silicate alteration reactions determine the stability of co-occurring carbonate minerals, and vice versa. Therefore, the dissolution/precipitation of carbonate and iron sulphide minerals directly control the buffering capacity of the solution and sets the feedbacks on the silicate reaction pathways.

Numerical modelling serves as a powerful tool to address the coupling between silicon and carbon (and potentially iron and sulfur) in marine sediments where pH is impacted by organic matter diagenesis (Ehlert et al., 2016; Luo et al., 2020; Hong et al., 2020a, 2020b; Mills et al., 2021; Meister et al., 2022; Ward et al., 2022; Geilert et al., 2023). Here, we perform a systematic sensitivity test with a numerical model that includes key diagenetic reactions (Hong et al., 2014; Torres et al., 2020; Luo et al., 2020; Sauer et al., 2021). The model is described in detail in the *Supplementary Material (Section 7.1)*. Briefly, we focus on the conditions that involve in three early diagenetic reactions: iron reduction, sulfate reduction, and methane generation from organic matter fermentation (Table 4 and Section 7.1 for details). Hydrolysis of particulate organic matter (POM) produces sugars that can be further fermented to produce dissolved hydrogen gas and organic compounds, such as acetate (Canfield et al., 2005). These compounds fuel various biogeochemical reactions in marine sediments (Table 4 and Section 7.1 for details), which in turn affect the stability of mineral and amorphous phases, such as carbonate, pyrite, opal, and silicates. In order to accurately describe the central role of pore fluid pH, we consider a full suite of primary and secondary dissolved species (Supplementary Table 1) together with the equilibrium reactions associated with these dissolved species (Supplementary Table 2).

We first describe four scenarios in our model that include various early diagenetic reactions:

- *Scenario 1*: Iron reduction coupled with oxidation of hydrogen gas produced from POM hydrolysis (Fig. 2a).
- *Scenario 2*: Sulfate reduction with oxidation of hydrogen gas and/or acetate produced from POM hydrolysis (Fig. 2b).
- *Scenario 3*: Active iron and sulfate reduction (Fig. 2c).
- *Scenario 4*: In addition to sulfate and iron reduction, an external methane supply was assigned to the model bottom boundary, which induces anaerobic oxidation of methane (AOM) and thus accelerates

Table 4
Early diagenetic reactions included in modelling scenarios. See Section 7.1 in the Supplementary material for the full equations.

	Reactant(s)	Product(s)	Note
POM hydrolysis	POM	Sugar, NH ₄ ⁺ , and HPO ₄	
Fermentation	Sugar	H _{2(aq)} , acetate, HCO ₃	
Hydrogentrophic sulfate reduction, H ₂ -SR	SO ₄ ²⁻ and H ₂ (aq)	HS ⁻ and H ₂ O(l)	
Acetotrophic sulfate reduction, Ac-SR	SO ₄ ²⁻ and acetate	HS ⁻ and HCO ₃	
Hydrogentrophic iron reduction, H ₂ -FeR	FeOOH(s) and H ₂ (aq)	Fe ²⁺ and H ₂ O(l)	
Anaerobic oxidation of methane, AOM	CH _{4(aq)} and H ₂ O(l)	H _{2(aq)} and HCO ₃	Prescribed as forward and reverse of the same reaction
Hydrogentrophic CO ₂ reduction (methanogenesis), H ₂ -ME	H _{2(aq)} and HCO ₃	CH _{4(aq)} and H ₂ O(l)	
Calcium carbonate precipitation/dissolution	CaCO _{3(s)}	HCO ₃	Direction of the reaction depends on mineral saturation and thus pore fluid composition
Pyrite precipitation/dissolution	FeS _{2(s)}	Fe ²⁺ and HS ⁻	
SiO _{2(s)} precipitation/dissolution	SiO _{2(s)}	H ₄ SiO _{4(aq)}	

sulfate reduction. Microbial methanogenesis, which was inhibited by sulfate in previous scenarios, becomes thermodynamically feasible in this scenario and produces additional methane besides the external source prescribed in the model (Fig. 2d).

It becomes apparent that early diagenetic reactions affect pore fluid pH (Boudreau and Canfield, 1993; Hong and Reible, 2013), with iron reduction and fermentation being the two critical processes that drive pH changes. Iron reduction consumes a large amount of protons when reducing Fe(III) (Supplementary Eq. (3)) and thus leads to basic pore fluid conditions (Fig. 2a). Sulfate reduction driven by organic matter degradation lowers pore fluid pH when iron reduction is absent (Supplementary Eq. (4) and Fig. 2b). However, in natural sediments, it is rare that sulfate reduction occurs alone without concurrent iron reduction. More commonly, sulfate and iron reduction co-occur, resulting in the precipitation of iron sulphide minerals, which increases pore fluid pH (Fig. 2c). On the other hand, fermentation of glucose releases acetic and carbonic acids (Supplementary Eq. (2)) and lowers pore fluid pH below the sulfate reduction zone where no electron acceptors are present with substantial concentrations (Fig. 2d). Our simulated downcore pore fluid profiles cover the pH ranges that have been reported by shipboard analyses (Fig. 2e-2h) and thus provide confidence that the modelled results reflect the actual pore fluid conditions that are critical for our considerations on the stability of silicate minerals.

3.2. Stability of silicate phases under early diagenetic conditions

We modelled the saturation of 90 silicate minerals that cover major silicate groups as listed in Table 2 (see Supplementary Table 3 for detailed list of silicates included in the modelling). Admittedly, the coverage of silicate minerals in our model is far from complete and limited by the availability of thermodynamic parameters in the databases used. Nonetheless, this selection meant to cover the two types of detritus silicate minerals in marine sediments discussed previously in Section 2.1: 1) end-member minerals in the solid-solution series of rock-forming primary mineral groups (e.g., enstatite-ferrosilite for orthopyroxene, fayalite-forsterite for olivine, tremolite-pargasite for amphibole, microcline-albite-anorthite for feldspar, and phlogopite-annite-siderophyllite for biotite); 2) detritus clay minerals groups that are common in marine sediments. The saturation of these silicates was determined by the ratio between ion activity product (IAP) and the respective K_{sp} (i.e. $\log_{10}(\text{IAP}/K_{eq})$, with K_{sp} listed in Supplementary Table 3) that is included in the $f(\Delta G_r)$ term of Eq. (3). The IAP thus accounts for the activities of relevant dissolved species and most importantly pH.

As a first step in our modelling approach, the modelled 90 silicate minerals were set to be unequilibrated and non-reactive, i.e. only passively affected by the changes in the pore fluid composition that result from the different early diagenetic reactions in the four scenarios considered (Fig. 2). Dissolved aluminium concentration was set at 10 nM and remained invariable throughout the silicate stability simulations, as no silicate minerals were allowed to react. An amorphous SiO_{2(s)} phase (i.e. opal) was enabled to react in the model (Table 4), which controls porewater silica concentration.

Results of this exercise show that most of the feldspar group silicates are oversaturated in all scenarios, except for anorthite, which tends to dissolve if the sediments are sulfidic with low pore fluid pH (e.g., Scenario 2, sulfate reduction alone, Fig. 3 and Supplementary Table 4). Other primary silicates such as olivine, pyroxene, and amphibole, tend to dissolve in all scenarios. Dissolution of these primary silicates has been well documented along the mid-ocean ridge as an important marine silicate weathering mechanism (i.e. alteration of oceanic crust in Table 1). Illite and zeolite group silicates are always oversaturated (i.e. tend to precipitate) regardless of the combination of reactions considered (Fig. 3). Most of the phases in the SiO_{2(s)} & kaolinite groups, e.g., quartz, kaolinite, and halloysite, are oversaturated in all scenarios,

Fig. 2. (a)-(d) Pore fluid methane, sulfate, iron, and pH downcore profiles for the four scenarios simulated that include FeR: iron reduction; SR: sulfate reduction; and ME: methanogenesis. The modelled profiles are generic and do not necessarily fit with any of the study sites. Nonetheless, these generic profiles agree with the general trends observed in the porewater data as illustrated in (e)-(h).

except for opal that is always undersaturated (Fig. 3). On the other hand, the saturation of smectite and mica group silicates varies across the pH range simulated in the different scenarios (Fig. 3). These silicate groups are therefore more likely to buffer changes in pH as a result of early diagenetic reactions.

We considered nine types of vermiculite and 46 different smectite silicates of four major groups (montmorillonite, saponite, nontronite, and mixed-layer smectite-illite) (Supplementary Table 3). Not only did we consider the hydrated and non-hydrated silicates, but we also included the substitution of different elements into the mineral arrangement. For example, we considered eight hydrated montmorillonite phases and another eight non-hydrated ones. These variations have different cation (Mg^{2+} , Ca^{2+} , K^+ , and Na^+) in the mineral interlayers. Among these minerals, nontronite (both hydrated and non-hydrated) and vermiculite (hydrated) tend to dissolve in all conditions considered (Fig. 3). This result has also been documented in another similar modelling assessment (Meister et al., 2022). Montmorillonite is the most stable smectite group silicate for the entire pH range considered. Saponite tends to dissolve under acidic pore fluid conditions when only sulfate reduction is considered (Scenario 2 and Fig. 3b) but is stable under basic pore fluids when iron reduction is coupled to sulfate reduction (Scenario 3 and Fig. 3a&3c). Below the sulfate reduction zone, when pH is further lowered by continuous organic matter fermentation, saponite tends to dissolve (Fig. 3d).

The six different mica group silicates considered are: muscovite, glauconite, phlogopite-K, phlogopite-Na, annite, and siderophyllite. Muscovite is always oversaturated and tends to precipitate. Annite tends

to dissolve in acidic porewater (Fig. 3b&3d). Phlogopite-K and siderophyllite are undersaturated in the acidic pore fluids of Scenario 2 (Fig. 3b) and below the sulfate reduction zone for Scenario 4 (only for siderophyllite, Fig. 3d). Glauconite is almost always slightly undersaturated for all scenarios, which contradicts the observations of authigenic glauconite minerals in shallow marine sediments (Abbott et al., 2019; López-Quirós et al., 2019; Geilert et al., 2024 and Supplementary Table 5) and the common notion that glauconite forms authigenically in deep-sea settings (Baldermann et al., 2013, 2022; López-Quirós et al., 2019). This contradiction likely due to the fact that, our simulated scenarios do not cover diagenetic environments above the iron reduction zone (i.e., not covering oxic as well as nitric and manganese reducing sediments) where glauconite authigenesis is believed to occur. For example, Baldermann et al. (2013) proposed the mechanism for deep sea glauconite formation based on the observations from the upper 25 m of sediments recovered from Hole 959C during ODP Leg 159 off Ivory Coast. Based on the shipboard porewater data (Shipboard Scientific Party, 1996), the initiation of iron reduction corresponds to the shallow-most sample with elevated porewater iron concentration at ca. 38 mbsf, or 13 m deeper than where the glauconite was documented in Baldermann et al. (2013). Within the iron reduction zone, ferric iron is subject to reduction which makes glauconite less favourable or even undersaturated as demonstrated in our modelled saturation profiles (Fig. 3a). This corroborates the conclusion made in Baldermann et al. (2013) that (ferric) iron supply limits glauconitization. In deeper sulfidic sediments, where dissolved iron is rapidly precipitated out as iron sulphide minerals, glauconite is undersaturated as suggested by our

Fig. 3. Saturation (expressed as $\log_{10}(IAP/K_{sp})$) of the 90 modelled silicate phases under the four different organic matter diagenetic scenarios investigated. Blue shading indicates oversaturation, while red colours denote undersaturation. Colour strength reflects the degree of oversaturation/undersaturation. Numbers from the bottom of the figure correspond to the numbers in Supplementary Table 4 that include the maximum, minimum, and average saturation of all modelled silicate phases for the different scenarios. (For interpretation of the references to colour in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the web version of this article.)

modelling results (Fig. 3d).

Through this analysis, we have established the various silicate mineral stabilities at the pH values expected under different early diagenetic conditions. This exercise allows us to focus on a few types of silicate minerals and examine how they interact with other silicate phases when dissolved aluminium and cation availability constitute additional factors determining the mineral stability. To this aim, in the next section we detail the predicted responses when our numerical model allows for different sets of silicate minerals to react concurrently with other early diagenetic reactions.

3.3. Interactions among silicate alteration, carbonate precipitation, and organic matter degradation

Here we focus on the scenario with a full set of early diagenetic

reactions (i.e. *Scenario 4* in Fig. 2), a condition that is common for the sites we will discuss in the Section 4. We tested 14 different combinations of silicate minerals (Fig. 4) and examined their reaction rates and resulting pore fluid profiles under two different organic matter decomposition rates: moderate and fast organic matter degradation as represented by the different kinetic constants for POM hydrolysis (Supplementary Table 2). In contrast to the model setup in Section 3.2, the different silicate minerals were allowed to react, with their saturation and reaction rates being determined by the pore fluid composition using the equations listed in Supplementary Table 3. Different mica-group silicates (phlogopite-K, siderophyllite, annite, and glauconite), plagioclase/alkali feldspar (anorthite and albite), olivine (forsterite and fayalite), pyroxene (diopside and enstatite), and amphibole (tremolite and pargasite) were considered one-by-one, in addition to the smectite-group silicate and opal, in our sensitivity tests.

Fig. 3. (continued).

The 32 porewater primary and secondary species included in the model (Supplementary Table 1) allow us to simulate total alkalinity (TA) of the system (Fig. 4).

In the model, DIC is calculated as:

$$DIC = [H_2CO_{3(aq)}] + [HCO_3^-] + [CO_3^{2-}] \quad (12)$$

while total alkalinity is calculated as the charge summation of all weak bases in solution minus the charge summation of all weak acids:

$$\begin{aligned} TA = & [HCO_3^-] + 2[CO_3^{2-}] + [HPO_4^{2-}] + 2 \times [PO_4^{3-}] - [H_3PO_{4(aq)}] \\ & + [HS^-] + 2[S^{2-}] + [H_3SiO_4^-] + [NH_{3(aq)}] + B(OH)_4^- \\ & + [CH_3COO^-] - [H^+] + [OH^-] \end{aligned} \quad (13)$$

To distinguish charge (and thus alkalinity) from concentration, we use milliequivalent per litre (meq/L) when referring to alkalinity, and

millimole per litre (mmol/L) when referring to the concentrations of different solutes (e.g., DIC, see Middelburg et al. (2020) and Zeebe and Wolf-Gladrow (2001) for further discussion).

For the *base-case* with a moderate organic matter degradation rate and without silicate alteration, the extended sulfate and iron reduction zones (sulfate-methane-transition-zone, SMTZ, at ca. 28.4 mbsf, Fig. 2d) result in a high pore fluid pH of up to 8.3 above the SMTZ and lower pH down to 7.3 below SMTZ (black solid line, Fig. 4a). Above the SMTZ, authigenic carbonate precipitates at high rates of up to 400 $\mu\text{mol}/\text{m}^3/\text{yr}$ (Fig. 4b). When smectite group silicates are included (*smectite-case* hereafter), formation of saponite and mix-layered smectite is favourable and could lower pore fluid pH if occurs (black dotted dash line in Fig. 4a). Carbonate precipitation rates from the *smectite-case* are only a quarter of the rates from the *base-case* scenario because of the resulting lower pH in the *smectite-case* (black dotted dash line in Fig. 4b & Table 5).

Fig. 4. Model sensitivity tests with 14 different silicate mineral pairs under a full suite of early diagenetic processes (Table 4). The grey-shaded areas mark the depth ranges of sulfate reduction zone. Black solid lines in all plots show results from a base-case that does not include any silicate minerals. Black dotted dash lines show the smectite-cases with 9 vermiculite and 46 smectite group silicates included. The other lines are model results with 9 vermiculite and 46 smectite group silicates and one additional silicate from the five mineral groups focused. Values in the parenthesis in the legend are the cation-to-Si ratios calculated for each silicate based on the values from Supplementary Table 3. Upper panel (a-d) show results from simulations with a moderate POM degradation rate with porewater data from Vestnesa Ridge (grey filled circles) as a comparison. Lower panels (e-h) reflect the fast organic matter degradation scenarios with porewater data from Ulleung Basin (UBGH2-1-1, grey filled circles, depth adjusted to fit with the model scenarios) as a comparison. Downcore TA profiles for all scenarios in (d) overlap with each other as TA level is well-buffered by carbonate formation in the scenarios of a moderate POM degradation rate. Downcore DIC concentrations were not presented as they also overlap and cannot be clearly differentiated. The complete porewater profiles from the two exemplary sites were shown in Supplementary Fig. 3.

When dissolution of reactive silicates were included in the model, downcore pH values of most scenarios generally range between the high values of the *base-case* and the low values of the *smectite-case* (black solid and dashed lines, respectively, in Fig. 4a) indicating a limited buffering capacity from dissolution of some modelled silicates. According to the model-predicted pH profiles and the ratios of cation-to-Si (Fig. 4), we can broadly classify all 12 modelled silicates into three categories:

- *Net reverse weathering*: Dissolution of albite (cation-to-Si ratio: 1.3) and tremolite (1.8) results in even lower pH as compared to that for the *smectite-case*.
- Dissolution of glauconite (1.9), diopside (2.0), and enstatite (2.0) results in similar downcore pH as to that for the *smectite-case*.
- *Net silicate weathering*: Dissolution of the rest seven reactive silicates (3.3 to 7) results in pH values higher than that of the *smectite-case*.

As the cation-to-Si ratio for the actively forming mix-layered smectite is 1.9, dissolution of any reactive silicates with ratios lower than this value (i.e. albite and tremolite) induces more clay formation, which further lowers porewater pH. Dissolution of silicate minerals with cation-to-Si ratios close to, or slightly higher than, the two forming clay minerals does not fully compensate for the acidity generated by clay formation and thus results in lower pH values relative to those from the *base-case* (i.e. net reverse weathering). On the other hand, when smectite formation is coupled to siderophyllite and pargasite dissolution, pH values can be maintained at levels that are only slightly lower than that

for the *base-case* (i.e. net silicate weathering, Fig. 4a and Table 5). Carbonate precipitation rates are heavily dependent on pore fluid pH and range between rates of *base-case* and *smectite-case* (Fig. 4b & Table 5). Despite the variation in pH and carbonate precipitation rates, downcore profiles of TA are almost identical for all the modelled scenarios under the moderate organic matter degradation rate (Fig. 4d).

For the *base-case* with a higher organic matter degradation rate (i.e. higher POM hydrolysis rate in the model, Table 4), a faster sulfate reduction rate results in a shallower SMTZ (ca. 10 mbsf) as compared to the SMTZ in the previous *base-case*. The extended methanogenesis zone allows for more organic matter fermentation that produces more H_2CO_3 (aq) and acidifies pore fluids (black solid in Fig. 4e), as compared to the *base-case* with a moderate organic matter degradation rate. Formation of authigenic carbonate and smectite remains thermodynamically favourable, but are much less active under the low porewater pH (black solid in Fig. 4f for carbonate formation). This means that both types of minerals lose most of the ability to buffer porewater pH and alkalinity as previously shown for the case with a moderate organic matter degradation rate. With the high organic matter degradation rate, pH from the *smectite-case* is only slightly higher than that for the *base-case* (black dotted dash and solid lines in Fig. 4e). Formation of Ca-rich saponite and mix-layered smectite forces other smectites to dissolve due to the low dissolved aluminium activity, and thus converts a small fraction of the fermentation-derived carbonic acid to alkalinity. Peak carbonate precipitation rates are lower for both *smectite-* and *base-cases* (blue and grey lines in Fig. 4f) as compared to the same cases where organic matter

Table 5

TA/DIC/H₂CO_{3(aq)} fluxes and carbonate precipitation rates for the different modelling scenarios (mod: moderate organic matter degradation, fast: fast organic matter degradation, TA: total alkalinity).

	mmol HCO ₃ ⁻ /m ² (bulk sediment)/yr						meq /m ² (bulk sediment)/yr							
	(i) F _{DIC} [*]		(ii) F _{CO_{2(aq)}} [*]		(iii) ∫ R _{CaCO₃}		(iv) F _{TA} [*]		(v) ΔF _{TA}		(vi) Δ∫ R _{CaCO₃} [‡]		(vii) (v) + (vi)	
	mod	fast	mod	fast	mod	fast	mod	fast	mod	fast	mod	fast	mod	fast
(a) Base-case	9.7	59.1	0.1	10.7	8.0	0.3	10.4	63.3	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0
(b) Smectite-case	10.6	59.0	0.5	8.3	3.1	0.9	10.5	66.4	0.2	3.1	-9.8	1.1	-9.6/ -50 % [†]	4.2/ 1 %
(c) Smectite + Anorthite	10.1	57.4	0.2	5.9	5.6	2.4	10.3	67.9	-0.1	4.6	-4.8	4.2	-4.9/ -25 %	8.7/ 4 %
(d) Smectite + Albite	10.7	59.1	0.6	8.5	2.7	1.0	10.6	66.1	0.2	2.7	-10.7	1.2	-10.5/ -55 %	3.9/ 1 %
(e) Smectite + Phlogopite-K	10.2	56.5	0.3	2.7	4.8	4.2	10.4	70.7	0.1	7.4	-6.4	7.6	-6.3/ -33 %	15.0/ 6 %
(f) Smectite + Annite	10.5	54.9	0.4	4.4	4.4	2.6	10.3	60.7	0.0	-2.6	-7.3	4.6	-7.3/ -38 %	2.0/ 4 %
(g) Smectite + Siderophyllite	9.7	57.5	0.1	6.5	9.0	1.3	10.1	66.5	-0.3	3.2	2.0	1.9	1.7/ 10 %	5.0/ 2 %
(h) Smectite + Forsterite	10.5	57.4	0.4	4.2	3.8	2.8	10.5	69.0	0.1	5.7	-8.5	4.9	-8.3/ -44 %	10.5/ 4 %
(i) Smectite + Enstatite	10.6	58.4	0.5	6.1	3.1	1.8	10.5	67.7	0.2	4.4	-9.8	2.9	-9.6/ -50 %	2 %
(j) Smectite + Pargasite	9.3	52.7	0.1	1.4	10.0	17.8	9.8	69.8	-0.6	6.5	4.0	34.9	3.5/ 21 %	41.4/ 30 %

^{*} Calculated by using Fick's first law with slopes of the linear regressions of modelled downcore TA and DIC concentration between 0.15 mbsf and the sulfate-methane-transition zone, 28.4 and 6.15 mbsf, respectively for the moderate and fast organic matter degradation conditions and a diffusion coefficient of 1.94×10^{-2} m²/yr for HCO₃⁻ at 4 °C. A constant porosity of 0.7 and a cementation factor of 1.5 were assumed to convert porewater flux to bulk sediment flux and to correct for tortuosity with the Archie's equation (Archie, 1942). See Supplementary Fig. 4 for examples.

[‡] Defined as the difference in carbonate alkalinity between the respective case and the Base-case: for example, $2 \times (4.2-0.3)$ for the case with phlogopite-K.

[†] Percentage of carbonate formation from total DIC production from organic matter: for example, $(4.2-0.3)/59.1 \times 100$ for the case with phlogopite-K.

degradation is moderate (Fig. 4b).

Cation-rich silicates become the last line of defence in buffering pore fluid pH under such a high organic matter degradation rate. Among all of the silicates considered in our simulation, pargasite and phlogopite-K are the most capable of buffering porewater pH, keeping pore fluids slightly basic. For example, by comparing the model results that involve phlogopite-K under high and moderate organic matter degradation rates, the resulting downcore pH values are stable between the range of 7 to 7.7 (Fig. 4a&4e). In comparison, the base-cases for both organic matter degradation rates have pH values in the range of 6.2 to 8.7 (Fig. 4a&4e), while the pH values for smectite-cases fall in the range of 6.5 to 7.5 (Fig. 4a&4e). High pH values are essential in keeping the partial pressure of CO₂ in the marine sediments low, as basic pore fluids retain DIC in the form of alkalinity. Indeed, high alkalinity values over ca. 56 meq/L, which cannot be explained by sulfate reduction alone, are generated from our model results (Fig. 4h) and have been observed along productive margins worldwide (Wallmann et al., 2008) as shown in Supplementary Fig. 3.

3.4. Limitation of the modelling approach

We note that, the model results for dissolution/precipitation of the different silicate phases need to be considered with caution due to the following limitation of our modelling approach:

- Sedimentation was not considered in the current model and thus no new supply of silicate and organic matter phases included in the model. Therefore, we were not able to derive precise time constraints for the processes with the current model.
- A proper kinetic expression for the nucleation and growth of clay minerals was not implemented (e.g., Steefel and Van Cappellen, 1990; Fritz et al., 2009). As a result, the current model may predict clay formation over-optimistically. In the model, nucleation of the clay minerals occurs when the solution is oversaturated.

- We did not consider any kinetic inhibition (and catalyst) for the silicate alteration processes. For example, dissolved aluminium has been shown to inhibit muscovite dissolution (Oelkers et al., 2008) while organic ligands and dissolved ammonium have been shown to promote dissolution of biotite and/or other mica group silicates (Bray et al., 2015; Lamarca-Irisarri et al., 2019). As a result, reactions that were calculated to be thermodynamically favourable by our modelling may not happen in nature due to the presence of inhibitors.

4. Controls of marine silicate alteration inferred from a data compilation of scientific deep-sea drilling programs

By coupling the kinetics of various marine silicate alteration reactions (Section 2) with our modelled-derived information on how silicate reactions interact with other early diagenetic processes (Section 3.2), we have assessed the stability of various types of silicate minerals that are common in hemipelagic environments. Despite the potential limitation of our model (Section 3.4), we have established the role of marine silicate alteration in buffering pore fluid pH through our numerical simulations, especially when organic matter is degraded at a high rate. In this section, we examine pore fluid composition compiled from various international scientific drilling programs to constrain the type of reactive silicates involved and the environmental factors that control their dissolution rates.

4.1. Weathering driven by dissolution of Mg- and K-containing silicate minerals

We performed an in-depth analysis of the pore fluid composition from 48 sites (Supplementary Fig. 2) that were selected either based on their high TA levels (>56 meq/L) or because of the indication of silicate alteration by geochemical tracers, despite the lower TA levels (<56 meq/L):

- **Group LAlk:** The 22 low alkalinity (<56 meq/L) sites with geochemical tracers such as the $^{87}\text{Sr}/^{86}\text{Sr}$ ratios (Solomon et al., 2014; Torres et al., 2020, 2022; Luo et al., 2020) and $\delta^{26}\text{Mg}$ signatures in porewater (Berg et al., 2019), used reflect marine silicate mineral dissolution and/or authigenic clay formation. For example, silicate dissolution can be inferred from deviation in $^{87}\text{Sr}/^{86}\text{Sr}$ ratios in porewater relative to coeval seawater values at sites with low alkalinity. The unexpected low alkalinity values motivate us to compare the measured porewater composition with our model results. The lower pore fluid ammonium concentrations measured at these sites (Fig. 6a), compared to the sites from the next group, correspond with our modelled scenario with moderate organic matter degradation (Fig. 4a to 4d).
- **Group HAlk:** The 26 hyper-alkalinity sites where the highest alkalinity exceeds 56 meq/L, i.e. doubled of seawater sulfate concentration (TA range: 68.3 meq/L to 265.7 meq/L), reveal intensive weathering driven by marine silicate dissolution. The indication of fast organic matter fermentation that promotes silicate weathering in this group is supported by high dissolved ammonium concentrations (Fig. 6). This group directly corresponds to our model scenarios with fast organic matter degradation (Fig. 4e to 4h).

With the aim to differentiate the contribution to TA from the different cations in all 48 sites investigated, we equated TA to the charge difference that considers all major cations and anions:

$$TA_x = POS_x - NEG_x \quad (14)$$

where *POS* and *NEG* refer to the total charge from major cation and anion, respectively ($POS = [\text{Na}^+] + [\text{K}^+] + 2[\text{Ca}^{2+}] + 2[\text{Mg}^{2+}] + [\text{NH}_4^+]$, $NEG = [\text{Br}^- + \text{Cl}^-] + 2[\text{SO}_4^{2-}]$), and *x* refers to the sample depth below seafloor. The multiplier “2” for calcium, magnesium, and sulfate converts concentration (in brackets) to charge for these solutes. The major cations and anions are defined as those porewater species that do not change their speciation in the pH range of ocean (e.g., 7-9). This is in contrast to the ions listed in Supplementary Table 2 that change their speciation within this pH range and contribute to the TA term to the right of Eq. (17).

Elevated alkalinity values have been taken as undisputable evidence for net silicate weathering (Wallmann et al., 2008; Kim et al., 2016). However, it is apparent from Eq. (14) that changes in both cation and anion concentrations contribute to alkalinity. Higher TA could be attributed to the increase of cation concentrations (thus *POS*) that results from silicate alteration, a decrease of anion concentrations (thus *NEG*), or a combination of both.

To compare the excess (or deficit) of charges that result from various in-situ processes among the different sites, we subtract the bottom water (BW) solute concentrations from that of pore fluids:

$$(POS_x - POS_{BW}) - (NEG_x - NEG_{BW}) = (TA_x - TA_{BW}) \quad (15)$$

This allows us to define the “cap” (Δ) values that quantify excess/deficit of charge relative to bottom water values:

$$\Delta POS_{x-BW} - \Delta NEG_{x-BW} = \Delta TA_{x-BW} \quad (16)$$

By plugging in the definitions of *POS* and *NEG*, we separate the contribution of TA from each cation and anion:

$$\Delta([\text{Na}^+] + 2 \times [\text{Mg}^{2+}] + 2 \times [\text{Ca}^{2+}] + [\text{K}^+] + [\text{NH}_4^+])_{x-BW} - \Delta(2 \times [\text{SO}_4^{2-}] + [\text{Br}^- + \text{Cl}^-])_{x-BW} = \Delta TA_{x-BW} \quad (17)$$

meteoric water, gas hydrate dissociation, clay dehydration influences (Kastner et al., 1991; Tomaru et al., 2006; Hong et al., 2019; Kim et al., 2022) can potentially complicate the calculation of in-situ TA contribution from the different cations. An approach to eliminate the effect of fluid mixing is to divide the values in Eq. (17) by $\Delta[\text{Cl}^-]_{x-BW}$. However, such an operation involves assumption that all dissolved Cl^- concentration changes result from the mixing with fluids other than bottom seawater. In addition, such a division results in extremely large values when pore fluid Cl^- concentrations are very close to bottom concentration (i.e. $\Delta[\text{Cl}^-]_{x-BW}$ approaches zero), which makes the visualization confusing. Therefore, we adopted Eq. (17) for our further discussion.

It becomes obvious when plotting the model results for the *base-case*, *smectite-case*, and for the other 12 cases of reactive silicate phases, the pore fluid composition from *Group HAlk* sites is different from the composition of *Groups LAlk* sites. The following observations can be made:

- 1) NH_4^+ alkalinity is significantly higher from *Group HAlk* sites as compared to that from the rest of sites (Fig. 6a).
- 2) Ca^{2+} only contributes to alkalinity when TA is below ca. 50 meq/L in *Group HAlk* sites and below ca. 10 meq/L in *Groups LAlk* sites. For samples with higher TA, consumption of Ca^{2+} lowers TA at similar levels among all sites, regardless of the group (Fig. 6b).
- 3) Mg^{2+} contributes to up to 40 % of TA in *Group HAlk* sites. For all the other samples in *Group LAlk* and part of the samples in *Group HAlk*, Mg^{2+} concentration is lower than seawater (i.e. $\Delta\text{Mg} < 0$), indicating a common consumption of Mg alkalinity in all groups (Fig. 7a & 7b). This has been noted in many previous works that suggest an omnipresence of Mg consumption potentially through clay formation (Sayles and Fyfe, 1973; Sayles and Mangelsdorf, 1979; Sayles, 1981; Sun et al., 2016; Berg et al., 2019; Wallmann et al., 2023).
- 4) While positive ΔK can be seen in both groups, samples from *Group HAlk* have higher ΔK values indicating a process producing more K alkalinity as compared to sites from *Group LAlk*. In addition, very few sites from *Group HAlk* have negative ΔK values, suggesting a lower net (or even negligible) consumption of K alkalinity as compared to sites from *Group LAlk* (Fig. 7c & 7d).
- 5) Contribution of alkalinity from Na^+ , as calculated from charge balance (instead of measured concentrations), can be seen between the two groups of sites with no apparent difference (figure not shown).

The distinct differences in NH_4^+ contribution between both groups are in accordance with our model results, which indicate that organic matter degradation plays a fundamental role in driving the state changes of silicates (Fig. 4). However, it is important to note that, some of the sites included in the *Group LAlk* and those sites discussed by Wallmann et al. (2023) have active POM degradation as inferred from the millimolar levels of porewater ammonium (Fig. 6a) and by shallow penetration of sulfate (less than tens of meters below seafloor). This observation indicates that POM degradation is likely not the only factor determining the pathway of marine silicate alteration (i.e., silicate weathering vs. reverse weathering).

Our modelled Ca alkalinity consumption matches the observed levels for all cases regardless of organic matter degradation rates (Fig. 7e & 7f), suggesting a reasonable model-predicted coupling between authigenic carbonate formation and silicate dissolution/authigenesis. The different

levels of porewater Mg^{2+} alkalinity between groups point to dissolution/precipitation of Mg-containing silicate phases, as evidenced by the fact that authigenic carbonate (e.g., high-Mg calcite and aragonite, the most

Changes in pore fluid Cl^- concentration resulting of fluid mixing, e.g.

common type of authigenic carbonate; Hong et al., 2014, 2024; Smrzka et al., 2020; Thiagarajan et al., 2020; Pierre et al., 2017) cannot provide sufficient Mg^{2+} alkalinity for the observed changes in pore fluids (see Supplementary Fig. 3 for exemplary sites). Similarly, the higher porewater K^+ alkalinity from Group HALK, as compared to bottom water concentration, indicate dissolution of K-containing silicate phases. Note that K^+ does not contribute significantly to the hyper TA (<10% as read from Fig. 7d), and the negative ΔK values from both Groups HALK & LALK indicate K consumption through clay formation.

While model results in Section 3.2 suggest that alteration for various silicate phases is thermodynamically feasible (Fig. 3), our model-data comparison reveals that the dissolution of Mg- and K-rich silicate phases are the primary marine silicate weathering pathways leading to the observed hyper TA and overall porewater composition in Group HALK sites. Our model predicts a release of Mg and K through dissolution of phlogopite-K and siderophyllite, two of the naturally-occurring end-member biotite minerals, that is comparable to the dataset (Fig. 7c). In contrast, other silicate phases are not capable of reproducing the excess Mg and K alkalinity values in our model (e.g., pyroxene, amphibole, and olivine group silicates). The ability of a Mg- and K- containing silicate (i.e. Vermiculite) in producing high alkalinity was also shown by Meister et al. (2022) through a similar modelling effort. Furthermore, we identified a platy silicate phase enriched in Mg and Fe using a scanning electron microscopy (SEM) coupled with energy dispersive X-ray spectroscopy (EDS) in samples from a location with high TA (Fig. 8 and Supplementary Table 6). The observation of such a Mg-rich silicate phase supports the potential link between its dissolution and high TA, though this inference is not definitive and warrants more future research.

Admittedly, biotite group silicates, such as phlogopite-K and siderophyllite, are not common in marine sediments (Warr, 2022). Its global distribution has not been well established except for a few regional studies where the biotite distribution was briefly investigated (Edwards and Goodell, 1969; Diekmann and Kuhn, 1999; Kim et al., 2007). Whether biotite dissolution is a plausible explanation for the high porewater Mg and K concentrations observed (i.e. Fig. 7a&7c) require further investigation. Nonetheless, biotite (or general mica) has been identified in samples from 21 sites (or 28 sites for mica) out of the 42 sites investigated (Supplementary Table 5). Even though biotite is only a minor or even trace silicate mineral in these, its presence provides a first-order support for the model-inferred biotite dissolution. We note here that, in order to explain the observed high porewater Mg concentrations (e.g., 100 mM, Fig. 6c), only ca. 0.3 wt% of phlogopite ($KMg_3AlSi_3O_{10}(OH)_2$), the Mg-rich biotite in the mica family, is needed assuming a porosity of 0.5 and a dry sediment density of 2.6 g/cm³. Quantifying such a low amount of biotite (or any silicate minerals) is very difficult through the conventional XRD method (Zhou et al., 2018). This may partly explain why biotite was unidentified in some of the sites in the Group HALK (Supplementary Table 5).

Biotite is known to be unstable under low temperature conditions of marine sediments and can readily be altered to chlorite (Eggleton and Banfield, 1985). Moreover, results of laboratory experiments have confirmed that biotite can dissolve at appreciable rates at the range of pH that is relevant to our model scenarios (Malmström and Banwart, 1997; Oelkers et al., 2008; Bray et al., 2015; Lamarca-Irisarri et al., 2019). The low ionic strength solution used in these experiments, however, may limit the applicability of these results to marine environments. Collectively, our model-predicted biotite dissolution could be a promising candidate reaction explaining the high porewater Mg, K, and TA observed at the investigated sites. Results from our study indicate that further research is needed to account for the role of kinetic inhibitors, to gain a better understanding of biotite distribution in global marine sediments, and to conduct laboratory experiments in seawater-like matrices.

When we include only smectite group clays in our model (i.e. *smectite-case*) and/or silicates from amphibole, pyroxene, and olivine groups,

the dissolution of these silicates elevates Mg alkalinity (Fig. 7a) but has a negligible effect on K alkalinity (Fig. 7c). A similar explanation could be made for the elevated Mg alkalinity in the modelled case involving anorthite dissolution, a silicate phase containing no Mg (Supplementary Table 3): the dissolution of Mg-rich smectite increases Mg alkalinity in conjunction with anorthite dissolution. When we include albite and annite dissolution, a net Mg alkalinity consumption is observed, due to fast smectite formation stimulated by the Al release from these dissolving silicate phases.

Dissolution of Ca-containing silicates, such as anorthite, diopside, and tremolite, not only cannot reproduce the observed high levels of porewater Mg and K (Fig. 7a & 7c), but also fails to explain the low Ca level observed in the porewater data from Group HALK sites (Fig. 7e). Dissolution of these silicates provides additional Ca for carbonate formation and thus cannot effectively lower porewater Ca alkalinity as compared with the coupling with other silicate phases (Fig. 7e). On the other hand, despite the lack of Ca in mica group (phlogopite-K, siderophyllite, annite, and glauconite), olivine group (fayalite and forsterite) and pyroxene group silicate (enstatite), the well-buffered porewater that results from their dissolution of these reactive silicates, favours carbonate formation. Coupling of smectite formation and dissolution of these silicates thus stimulates authigenic carbonate formation reflected in the observed consumption of Ca alkalinity. It is also worth noting that, sites with high porewater Ca alkalinity (up to 275.4 meq/L, Fig. 6b), resulting from basement alteration reactions usually have very low TA (<3 meq/L). This has been explained by intensive carbonate precipitation and Mg consumption by smectite formation during seawater-basalt interaction (Bischoff and Dickson, 1975; Seyfried and Bischoff, 1977; Sample et al., 2017; Voigt et al., 2020).

Pore fluid ⁸⁷Sr/⁸⁶Sr data in several Group LALK sites has been proposed as an indicator of silicate weathering (Solomon et al., 2014; Kim et al., 2016; Torres et al., 2020; Luo et al., 2020; Hong et al., 2020a, 2020b). However, here we show that the lower TA and distinct pore fluid composition (i.e. negative ΔMg and ΔK , Fig. 7d and f) from this group point to no net silicate weathering. As we have shown here, the production of carbonate alkalinity through silicate dissolution (as revealed by porewater ⁸⁷Sr/⁸⁶Sr) may not always be able to compensate the alkalinity consumption resulting from clay and carbonate formation (e.g., iv from Fig. 5a). In other words, not all marine silicate dissolution results in net marine silicate weathering. Net silicate weathering occurs only when dissolution of K- & Mg-containing silicates is promoted by fast POM degradation. Geochemical signatures, such as porewater ⁸⁷Sr/⁸⁶Sr, thus only indicate marine silicate dissolution but not necessarily net marine silicate weathering.

4.2. Environmental modulation of marine silicate weathering as inferred from our data compilation

Besides organic matter reactivity and the type of silicate involved, other environmental factors may also determine the occurrence and rate of marine silicate dissolution, which in turn determines TA levels and fluxes. We compare TA values and alkalinity fluxes (F_{TA}) from both Group HALK & LALK sites (at 2 mbsf, where the shallowest reliable data from drilling operations can be obtained (see Supplementary Table 7 for calculation and Supplementary Fig. 4 for examples) with water depth, temperature, and sediment age. The 48 sites studied range from 419 m to 5086 m in water depths, with no apparent correlation between either TA or F_{TA} values with water depth (Supplementary Fig. 5a) nor with sediment depths (Fig. 9a and b). Nonetheless, hyper TA and the corresponding F_{TA} are mostly observed at sediment depths shallower than ca. 200 m below seafloor (mbsf) (Fig. 9a and b) and in sediments with ages ranging from 50 kyr (Site 1234, Chilean margin) to almost 3 Myr (Site 688, Peru margin) (Supplementary Fig. 5b).

It may be expected that fast sedimentation would boost marine silicate weathering given the high supply of silicate minerals and POM to the seafloor. However, such an assumption is not supported by our data

Fig. 5. Schematic diagrams showing the coupling between forward & reverse silicate weathering and inorganic & organic particulate carbon in the sediments. (a) Under a moderate organic matter degradation rate, the model-predicted high porewater pH due to extended (i) iron and sulfate reduction favours (ii) carbonate and (iii) clay authigenesis. Both processes buffer porewater pH by converting carbonate alkalinity to carbonic acid. (iv) Dissolution of silicate minerals, and thus silicate weathering, is only marginally important for the overall carbon cycling. (v) Despite the net reverse weathering, very little $H_2CO_{3(aq)}$ diffuses into surficial sediments, as carbonate precipitation buffers $H_2CO_{3(aq)}$ level in the porewater (see Section 4.3 for further discussion). (vi) Dissolution of cation-poor silicate minerals and biological opal provide dissolved Al (dAl) and silica (dSi), respectively, for clay formation. (b) Net forward silicate weathering occurs at low porewater pH resulting from (vii) organic matter fermentation (viii) suppressed authigenesis of clay (i.e. reverse weathering) and carbonate minerals. The high acidity produced by organic matter fermentation can only be buffered by (iv) silicate weathering in this scenario with additional carbonate alkalinity being produced, which diffuses towards surficial sediments (see Section 4.3 for further discussion).

compilation. We found no apparent correlation between TA values (or F_{TA}) and average sedimentation rates (Fig. 9c and d). Instead, marine silicate weathering inferred from hyper TA values seems to occur in sites with average sedimentation rates ranging between 10^2 to 10^3 m/Myr (Fig. 9c). The lack of marine silicate weathering from sites with very high sedimentation rates could be explained by either a short burial time that is insufficient for the reactions to occur, or by a lack of a favourable combination of materials to sustain the reaction. In other words, in addition to the type of silicate being deposited, the silicate-to-organic matter-ratio in the input sediment could potentially be important. For locations with high terrestrial sediment input but low organic matter supply (i.e. high silicate to organic matter ratio in the Arctic Ocean, (Stein et al., 1994)), silicate weathering is likely weak as most of the sediment columns are still in iron and/or sulfate reduction zones due to the low supply, and thus overall degradation, of POM.

High temperature is also known to accelerate silicate mineral dissolution (Oelkers and Schott, 2001; Brantley et al., 2023) and could potentially be expected to have an effect in marine silicate weathering. However, we observed no correlation between the highest TA and sediment temperature (Fig. 9e) nor with the prevailing geothermal gradient (Supplementary Fig. 5c). Inspired by the knowledge that opal diagenesis depends on the length of burial time and temperature (Mizutani, 1977; Riech and von Rad, 1979; Pisciotto, 1981), we grouped various parameters to represent the burial thermal history below the sulfate reduction zone (i.e. the duration of time buried below sulfate reduction zone multiplied by the temperature difference, see Supplementary Table 7). We observed higher TA values at locations with higher thermal history below sulfate reduction zone (Fig. 9g). We observe different regression lines among the various sites illustrated in Fig. 9g, which we interpret as reflecting the different sediment sources (i.e. types of silicate mineral) among the different sites. For example, for all the drill sites from the Atlantic Ocean (black dots, Fig. 9g, $n = 27$), a

significant correlation (p -value < 0.05) can be observed between the highest TA and thermal history beneath the sulfate reduction zone. The rather low R-square value of this correlation ($R^2 = 0.29$) suggests that only a fraction of the variance can be explained (Holmes and Huber, 2018). In other words, thermal history is only one of the factors, in addition to POM degradation rates and the type of reactive silicates, that affect the TA level in marine sediments. The insignificant correlation for the sites from oceans other than Atlantic Ocean (grey dots, $p = 0.19$, Fig. 9g) may be a result of too few sites considered in the correlation ($n = 8$) and thus it is heavily impacted by the outliers (e.g., S997 in Fig. 9g). The potential association between net marine silicate weathering and the cumulative effect of geothermal conditions and burial time below sulfate reduction zone, or sediment thermal history as we defined earlier, may also explain why anomalously high TA was not observed at sites with seemingly high organic matter degradation rates (e.g., sites from the Group LALK and those discussed by Wallmann et al., 2023). Silicate minerals, such as biotite, need to be exposed to a suitable thermal history during their burial to be activated for marine silicate weathering.

4.3. Implications of marine silicate alteration on carbon cycling in marine sediments

Collectively, we have highlighted a few important controls for marine silicate alteration including the reactivity of POM, type of silicate minerals, and potentially thermal history of burial beneath the sulfate reduction zone notwithstanding a lack of a satisfactory statistical significance. It becomes obvious that marine silicate alteration has the ability to affect subsurface carbon cycling through interaction with particulate organic/inorganic carbon, therefore changing porewater pH, aqueous carbonate speciation, and saturation of carbonate minerals (Fig. 5). It is however unclear whether the hyper TA generated within a

few meters, or even a few hundred meters below the seafloor influences the bottom ocean chemistry.

The fluxes of TA and DIC (F_{TA} and F_{DIC} , respectively) were calculated from both compiled data and numerical simulations (see Supplementary Fig. 4 for demonstration of calculation). While the data-constrained F_{TA} and F_{DIC} were set to be the fluxes at 2 mbsf (see Supplementary Table 7 for details) the model-constrained fluxes were derived from the concentration gradients between 0.15 mbsf and sulfate-methane-transition zone (28.4 and 6.15 mbsf for the different scenarios of POM degradation, Table 5) and thus represent the fluxes towards oxic surficial sediments, an early diagenetic zone that is not covered in the model. For comparison, we also included the depth-integrated rate for carbonate precipitation ($\int R_{CaCO_3}$) and summarised all the fluxes and rates in Table 5.

Our data compilation allows us to estimate the difference in F_{TA} between sites with different silicate weathering potential and POM degradation rates. In sites with rapid organic matter degradation (Group HAlk) and thus net marine silicate weathering (e.g., UBGH2-1-1 in Fig. 9b), F_{TA} can be a factor of two to three higher than that in cold seep sites, which are characterised by rapid sulfate reduction and fast alkalinity production in the top tens of meters below seafloor (e.g., Vestnesa Ridge or VR in Fig. 9b). Three general observations can be made:

- (i) POM degradation rates and early diagenetic processes are the primary controls of F_{DIC} and F_{TA} . This is apparent when we compare the *base-cases* scenarios for sites with different POM degradation rates excluding the effect from silicate weathering reactions. We observe values for F_{DIC} and F_{TA} that are

approximately six times higher in the *base-case* with a four-fold higher POM degradation rates than those in the *base-case* with a moderate rate (*mod* vs. *fast* in row **a** and columns **i** and **iv**, Table 5). Marine silicate weathering is only of secondary importance in controlling F_{TA} . This point can be further elaborated on by comparing the F_{TA} in scenarios with silicates dissolution and that from the *smectite-case* (Table 5, *fast* in rows **b** to **g** and column **iv**). How much of the TA survives transport across the oxic layer before it reaches the bottom ocean cannot be addressed in this study. Nonetheless, given the expected thin oxic sediment layers expected under a fast organic matter degradation (Cai and Sayles, 1996; Jørgensen et al., 2022), it is likely that fast POM degradation, in concert with marine silicate dissolution, could substantially increase benthic TA fluxes.

- (ii) Under an overall basic condition with moderate organic matter degradation, clay formation and carbonate precipitation are the primary buffer for pore fluid pH, with silicate dissolution playing a very minor role (except for siderophyllite). Clay and authigenic carbonate formation compete for the TA produced from iron/sulfate reduction. Clay formation reduces the precipitation rate of authigenic carbonate that can be inferred from the two-to-three times lower carbonate formation rates in the *smectite-case* than those in the *base-case* (i.e. negative $\Delta \int R_{CaCO_3}$ value, *mod* in column **vi** and row **b**, Table 5). Only negligible changes in F_{TA} can be detected between the *base* and *smectite* cases (*mod* in column **iv** and rows **a** & **b**, Table 5, or Fig. 4d).
- (iii) When pore fluid becomes acidic at sites with high POM degradation rates, precipitation of carbonate and clay minerals

Fig. 6. Change in pore fluid composition from the studied sites (orange: Group LAlk; blue: Group HAlk). Contribution of various cations to TA was estimated according to Eq. (17), and “ Δ ” refers to the difference between pore fluid and bottom seawater. Base-cases model results from Fig. 4 were also plotted for comparison in (a) and (b) as crosses with colour corresponding to the different particulate organic matter (POM) degradation rates (orange: moderate POM degradation; blue: high POM degradation). Dashed boxes in (b) to (d) are areas being enlarged in Fig. 7. Different patterns in pore fluid composition were observed between the different groups of data, hinting to fundamentally different silicate alteration processes in response to POM degradation rates. (For interpretation of the references in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the web version of this article.)

becomes less favourable, with lower overall reaction rates (Table 5; *fast* in column *iii* and row *a&b*). The effect of silicate dissolution in buffering pore fluid pH and preventing a decrease in pH becomes apparent in this scenario. This is clearly illustrated in the case of high POM degradation with, for example, phlogopite-K and pargasite (Fig. 4e), of which 15 and 41.4 meq/m²/yr, respectively, of TA production is predicted (Table 5, *fast* in column *vii* and row *e* and *j*). About half of the produced TA through dissolution of these reactive silicates diffuses towards the oxic sediments while the other half is fixed by authigenic carbonate formation (Table 5, *fast* in columns *iv* and *iii*, row *e*). More carbonate authigenesis is stimulated by pargasite dissolution due to abundant Ca in the amphibole (Table 5, *fast* in columns *vi*, row *e*).

Our model-data comparison highlights the potential of marine silicate alteration in providing TA to the oxic sediments, which largely consists of Mg, NH₄, and K alkalinity as indicated by the positive Δ values in Fig. 6. Such a result, however, may seem conflicting with the recent global estimates by Wallmann et al. (2023a) who concluded that marine silicate alteration serves as a sink for both Mg and K. There are two important points that needed to be clarified between our conclusion and theirs:

- (i) The marine silicate alteration defined by Wallmann et al. (2023) is similar to our model scenario with moderate POM degradation rates that with lower overall pore fluid TA (i.e. Fig. 4a-4d as well as Group *LALK* sites from Fig. 7b, d, and f). This is evident from the pore fluid data they used in their simulations, which has TA levels below the 56 meq/L threshold. As we elaborated earlier, in sites with moderate organic matter degradation rates, the overwhelming clay formation precludes *net* silicate weathering. From this perspective, the two studies arrive at a similar conclusion when considering the marine silicate weathering impact on TA under the moderate POM degradation rates.
- (ii) The critical difference between the two studies lies in the type of marine silicate being weathered. Based on their previous results (Wallmann et al., 2008), the authors assume anorthite to be the major silicate phase undergoing weathering (Wallmann et al., 2023). Based on our simulations, which include a full treatment of silicate reaction kinetics (Section 2.2) and mineral thermodynamic stability under various diagenetic fluid compositions (Section 3.2), we show that the mica-group silicates are equally, if not more, capable of undergoing weathering compared to anorthite (Fig. 4e-4h). In addition, the high Mg and K alkalinity measured in pore fluids in sites with hyper TA (Fig. 6) and the observation of Mg-rich silicate phases (Fig. 8), support our conclusion of a high TA flux, and a Mg and K source, from dissolution of Mg- and K-rich mica group silicates experiencing high POM degradation rates. The global contribution of TA to shallow sediment that results from *net* mica-group silicate weathering is currently lacking and awaits further investigation.

Our results have implications for the authigenic carbonate inventory in the deep methanogenic sediment. Phlogopite-K dissolution stimulates an additional alkalinity production of 15 meq/m²/yr (column *vii* in Table 5). Among the excess TA, 7.6 mmol/m²/yr is sequestered as authigenic carbonate (column *vi* in Table 5), or 51 % of the *additional* alkalinity produced, as compared to the *base-case* without any silicate reaction. Different types of silicate have variable capability in sequestering the additional TA produced by silicate weathering as carbonate minerals, which ranges from 27 % to 84 % with the two highest percentages calculated from pargasite and phlogopite-K dissolution (Table 5). Note that when dissolution of annite is considered, the high rate of authigenic carbonate formation even results in a reduction of F_{TA} towards shallow sediments (column *v* in Table 5).

We are able to comment on previous estimates for authigenic carbonate formation within methanogenic sediments initially presented by Wallmann et al. (2008) and later revised by Akam et al. (2023). In both papers, the amounts of DIC fixed as carbonate were based on stoichiometric relationships among organic carbon, methane, DIC, and carbonate, based on modelling of two profiles from Sea of Okhotsk and described by Eq. (27) of Wallmann et al. (2008), which we reproduce here:

Here, two moles of organic carbon (C(H₂O)) can produce 2/3 mol of HCO₃⁻ and 1/3 mol of authigenic carbonate (the latter fraction was assumed to be 1/2 by Akam et al. (2023)) with the rest one mole of organic carbon forming methane through CO₂ reduction. Carbonate precipitation rate was thus assumed to be 1/3 (Wallmann et al., 2008) to 1/2 (Akam et al., 2023) of the global methanogenesis rate, or 17 % and 25 %, respectively, of the organic matter degradation rate through methanogenesis (i.e. 2/3 mol of HCO₃⁻ and 1/3 mol of carbonate, respectively, divided by two mole of C(H₂O) in Eq. (18)).

To be able to compare our results with these estimates, we need to present our mass balance from the perspective of DIC (instead of TA), and compare the cases where silicate minerals are involved with the case without (i.e. *base-case*). For example, the 4.2 mmole C/m²/yr of carbonate being precipitated when considering phlogopite-K (*fast* in column *iii* and row *e*), corresponds to only 7 % of the F_{DIC} produced in the *base-case* (*fast* in column *i* and row *a* in Table 5). The F_{DIC} in the *base-case* corresponds to the DIC generated from POM degradation through methanogenesis. Such a percentage is substantially smaller than the published estimates of 17 to 25 %. A comparable percentage may be estimated if carbonate authigenesis is stimulated by pargasite dissolution, or 30 % of carbon produced from methanogenesis can be fixed as authigenic carbonate. These results show that the amounts of carbon sequestered as carbonate through *net* silicate weathering depend highly on the type of dissolving silicate minerals. A global estimate of such a deep subsurface carbonate inventory can only be constrained if the involving silicate mineral phases is understood.

Our model results also provide a first-order quantification on how reverse weathering in the iron/sulfate reduction zone could increase DIC and H₂CO_{3(aq)} fluxes to surface sediments, or potentially bottom seawater as previously assumed (Isson and Planavsky, 2018; Li et al., 2021). In sediments with moderate POM degradation rates, we estimated that the increase in F_{DIC} that results from faster reverse weathering and slower carbonate authigenesis, could be as high as 10 % (e.g., for the albite+smectite case) when compared to the *base-case* (10.6 vs. 9.7 mmol/m²/yr, respectively, Table 5, column *i*). We estimated a five-fold increase in $F_{CO_2(aq)}$ towards the oxic sediments between these two cases, from 0.1 to 0.5 mmol/m²/yr, as a result of net reverse weathering (Table 5, *mod* in column *ii*). If dissolution of a more cation-rich silicate is involved, such as phlogopite-K, the increase of $F_{CO_2(aq)}$, as compared to the *base-case* flux, is much less (0.3 vs. 0.1 mmol/m²/yr, *mod* in column *ii*, Table 5), as the additional cation release from silicate dissolution reduces alkalinity loss from reverse weathering (i.e. slower *net* reverse weathering). This result resembles our discussion about Group *LALK* sites (Section 4.1) in that, despite the dissolution of cation-rich silicate, faster formation of cation-rich clay still results in net reverse weathering and CO₂ production.

It is important to note that even higher $F_{CO_2(aq)}$ values were estimated for the Group *HALK* sites, i.e. sites with fast POM degradation even when they experience high rates of net marine silicate weathering (Table 5, *fast* in column *ii*). For example, $F_{CO_2(aq)}$ in the case of fast POM degradation and phlogopite-K dissolution is 27 times higher than the $F_{CO_2(aq)}$ of the *base-case* with a moderate organic matter degradation rate (Table 5), despite the active marine silicate weathering and enhanced

(caption on next page)

Fig. 7. Comparison of model results (crosses) and the data observations (filled circles). (blue: Group HAlk; orange: Group LAlk) See Fig. 6 for data overview. “ Δ ” refers to the difference between pore fluid and bottom seawater composition. (a&b) Contribution of Mg alkalinity under high particulate organic matter (POM) degradation rate and moderate POM degradation rate was reproduced by considering different silicate phases (Sme: smectite, Fors: forsterite, Faya: fayalite, Parg: pargasite, Tremo: tremolite, Ens: enstatite, Dio: diopside, Glauc: glauconite, Phl: phlogopite-K, Sid: siderophyllite, Ann: annite, An: anorthite, Ab: albite.). See Supplementary Table 3 for the cation composition of different silicate phases. (c&d) Our modelling K concentrations also match with data compilation which confirms that dissolution of Mg- and K-containing silicate phases is able to neutralize pore fluids (i.e. weathering) by releasing Mg and K. (e&f) Despite the dependency of carbonate precipitation on the type of weathered silicate (e.g., Fig. 4b & 4f), similar overall ranges of Ca^{2+} alkalinity consumption between the two groups of sites with contrasting TA levels were observed. This suggests the high TA is not a result of carbonate weathering nor that the high TA conditions from silicate weathering stimulates more authigenic carbonate formation. (For interpretation of the references to colour in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the web version of this article.)

Fig. 8. SEM image and EDS data from a sediment sample from East/Japan Sea (UBGH2-1_1). (a)-(c) SEM imaging was performed on carbon sputter coated thin sections at the Lund University Department of Geology using a variable pressure Mira3 High Resolution Schottky FE-SEM equipped with an Oxford EDS system. (c) Mapping of elements performed by the EDS system. The two red crosses (marked as p1 and p2 in (b)) indicate sample locations where point analyses for detailed element quantification were made (Supplementary Table 6). (For interpretation of the references to colour in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the web version of this article.)

(caption on next page)

Fig. 9. Highest TA and TA flux (at 2 mbsf) versus (a&b) sediment depth, (c&d) average sedimentation rate, (e&f) sediment temperature, and (g) thermal history below sulfate reduction (SR) zone. See the footnote of Supplementary Table 7 for the calculation of average sedimentation rate and thermal history below SR zone. Blue and orange points from (a-f) are sites from Group HALk and Group LALk sites, respectively. In (g), data points were arranged by regions, rather than TA levels, with the grey circles denoting sites from the Atlantic Ocean as indicated by the site number. Notice that only 35 sites have data available for the calculation of thermal history. The insignificant correlation for data points from African and South American margins ($R^2 = 0.27$, p -value = 0.19, $n = 8$) may be due to the limited data points available for regression. (For interpretation of the references to colour in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the web version of this article.)

F_{TA} . This is expected from our early discussion where we showed that the rate of POM degradation is the primary control for F_{DIC} and F_{TA} , and thus also $F_{CO2(aq)}$. Silicate alteration, in this case, plays only a secondary role in determining the overall fluxes of carbon towards the surficial sediments.

5. Conclusions

Through a modelling approach, we investigate the cooperation and competition of the two feedback loops: the particulate organic/inorganic carbon and the forward/reverse silicate weathering. Fundamentally, silicate (or opal) dissolution and clay formation are behind all silicate alteration processes (Fig. 5), while it is the different cation content in the reactive silicate phases that determines whether the overall reaction consumes carbonate alkalinity (i.e. net reverse weathering) or $H_2CO_{3(aq)}$ (i.e. net silicate weathering) as illustrated in Fig. 1. The different POM degradation rates and early diagenetic conditions, determine the initial porewater pH values and thus favour different silicate alteration processes. Our modelling approach, based on kinetics and thermodynamics considerations, allow us to quantify changes in DIC and TA fluxes as well as carbonate precipitation rates for different combinations of silicate minerals expected to react under contrasting POM degradation rates.

Net reverse weathering in the iron- & sulfate-reducing conditions of moderate POM degradation rates lowers porewater pH and rates of carbonate authigenesis, and consequently increases DIC fluxes towards the oxic sediments. In these moderate POM degradation sites, the predicted downcore TA values and TA fluxes are almost unaffected in the coupled carbon-silicate network, as the alkalinity consumption (via clay formation) is compensated by the reduction in carbonate authigenesis rates. In contrast, net silicate weathering in the methanogenic sediments found in sites with high POM degradation rates, results in increases in porewater pH, carbonate authigenesis rates, and TA fluxes towards the surface sediment, relative to the scenario without silicate weathering.

By examining a global dataset, we note a fair correlation between the highest TA from individual sites with their thermal history below the sulfate reduction zone. Such an observation may suggest that, similar to opal diagenesis, the dissolution of silicate phases (i.e. marine silicate weathering) depends on both the time of burial and geothermal heating. This conclusion however requires further examination as the correlation is not always significant. By comparing our model results with porewater data, we show that marine silicate weathering operates through dissolution of Mg- and K-containing mica-group silicates. This conclusion contrasts previous inferences of Ca-plagioclase (i.e. anorthite) as the primary phase for marine silicate weathering. Dissolution of anorthite, though favourable under the acidic porewater conditions in methanogenesis zone, results in a low pH buffering capacity compared to other mica-group silicates, and thus anorthite weathering cannot generate the same amounts of alkalinity as the Mg- and K-containing mica-group silicates (Fig. 4h).

Our revised marine silicate alteration scheme (Fig. 1), which combines mica-group silicate dissolution and smectite-group silicate formation, ties the diagenesis of these silicate phases to the changes in porewater pH, carbonate alkalinity, and major pore water composition. The silicate feedback loop then interacts with the carbon feedback loop involving aqueous carbonate species and particulate inorganic/organic carbon in the marine sediments. The coupling between the particulate organic-inorganic carbon loop and the forward-reverse silicate

weathering loop determines burial and cycling of carbon as well as other major constituents in marine sediments, which has a large potential to affect mass exchange across sediment-water interface.

CRediT authorship contribution statement

Wei-Li Hong: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Validation, Software, Resources, Project administration, Methodology, Investigation, Funding acquisition, Conceptualization. **Xiaole Sun:** Writing – review & editing, Investigation, Conceptualization. **Marta E. Torres:** Writing – review & editing, Investigation, Conceptualization. **Tzu-Hao Huang:** Writing – review & editing, Formal analysis. **Rebecca A. Pickering:** Writing – review & editing, Methodology, Formal analysis.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Appendix A. Supplementary data

Supplementary data to this article can be found online at <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.chemgeo.2025.122769>.

Data availability

Data used are from open databases and open access journals.

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